

Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg

Institute of Physics

Postgraduate Programme Renewable Energy

Master's Thesis

Title:

Simulation of photovoltaic-thermal (PV-T) solar assisted heat pump (SAHP) systems for building thermal demands

Presented by: *Pranay Kasturi*

First Examiner: *Dr. Herena Torio*

Second Examiner: *Prof. Dr. Carsten Agert*

Place, Date: *Hyderabad, 20.09.2023*

Declaration

I state and declare that this master thesis was prepared by me and that no means or sources have been used, except those, which I cited and listed in the References section. The master thesis is in compliance with the rules of good practice in scientific research of Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg.

Hyderabad, 20.09.2023

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank Mr. Jan Sören Schwarz, who helped me in the development of the models used in this work, and provided valuable feedback on the document.

I would like to also thank my supervisor, Dr. Herena Torio, without whose incredible support, patience, motivation and guidance, this work would not have been possible.

Finally, I would like to thank my family and friends, for standing by me through this testing time. Any amount of gratitude expressed to them would be insufficient.

Abstract

Heat pumps are becoming increasingly acknowledged as a pivotal technology in the effort to reduce carbon emissions from heating and coupling the heat pumps with renewable energy sources will be critical in their decarbonization. In this context, the use of photovoltaic thermal (PV-T) collectors to assist the heat pumps is expanding, due to the ability of such collectors to generate both electrical and thermal energy that can be exploited by the heat pump. The main objective of this study is to simulate the combined operation of PV-T and heat pump systems in meeting the building thermal demands, in order to evaluate the potential benefits that can be achieved with the said combined operation.

In order to achieve this objective, firstly, the basis for the simulations is established, in terms of the appropriate system configuration and system size for the thermal demands in consideration. Then the models required for the simulations -the heat pump model, the PV-T collector model, the hot water tank model, and the collector model- are developed. The developed detailed heat pump model is then functionally validated against an existing simplified heat pump model, establishing its higher suitability to the study, particularly at low temperature lift conditions that result from the combined operation of the PV-T and heat pump systems. The validated heat pump model is then used to perform the system simulations for a baseline scenario, without the PV-T system and with only the heat pump operating to supply the demands. Finally, the systems simulations are performed for the different configurations of the PV-T system, with 2,4,6,8,10 and 12 panels connected in series.

The comparison of the results from the simulations with the different configurations of the PV-T system shows that an increase in the number of panels in series leads to higher heating capacities and average COP of the heat pump, due to the higher source air temperatures achieved, leading to a reduction in the total electrical energy consumed by the system, and the share of the grid electrical energy used. However, the relative improvement in the performance of the system obtained by adding more panels in series, reduces, as the number of panels increase. Therefore, the configuration of the PV-T system with 4 panels in series, with an increase in the average COP of 6.61% and a decrease in the total electrical energy consumed of 6.17%, as compared to the baseline scenario, is found to be optimal for the building thermal demands in consideration. For the PV-T system configuration with 4 panels in series, an additional simulation is performed with an advanced control strategy aimed at increasing its operation during the daytime when the heat pump can benefit from the simultaneous operation with the PV-T system. When compared to the previous results of the same configuration with a regular control strategy, the average COP of the heat pump decreases by 1.9% and the total electrical energy consumed increases by 1.7%. However, due to the increase in daytime operation, when the PV-T system and the heat pump operate together, the self-consumption of the electrical energy of the PV-T system increases by 19% and the grid electrical energy used decreases by 5.5%. While only the technical comparison of the system performance has been done in this study, the comparison could be extended in further works to include economic and sustainability criteria to gain key insights into the practical implementation of such systems.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Motivation	1
1.2	Objectives	1
1.3	Structure of the report.....	2
2	Theory	3
2.1	Photovoltaic Thermal (PV-T) Solar Assisted Heat Pump (SAHP) systems.....	3
2.2	Approaches to model heat pump performance	4
2.3	Heat pump performance at low temperature lifts	4
3	Methodology	6
3.1	Basis for the scenario simulations	6
3.1.1	System configuration.....	6
3.1.2	Demands.....	7
3.1.3	Input data.....	8
3.2	Development of the models.....	9
3.2.1	Heat pump	9
3.2.2	Hot water tank	17
3.2.3	Photovoltaic-Thermal (PV-T) collector system	18
3.2.4	Controller.....	23
3.2.5	Co-simulation	28
3.3	Validation of the heat pump model	29
3.4	PV-T SAHP system simulations.....	30
4	Results	32
4.1	Validation	32
4.1.1	Simulations with reduced demands	32
4.1.2	Selection of heat pump model for further system simulations	41
4.2	Baseline scenario simulation	41
4.3	PV-T SAHP system simulations.....	45
4.3.1	Simulations of different configurations of PV-T system.....	45
4.3.2	Simulations of only the PV and the heat pump system	55
4.3.3	Simulation with the advanced control strategy.....	56
5	Conclusion	63
5.1	Limitations and scope for future research	64
	References	65
	Appendix A	67
	Appendix B	70

List of Figures

Figure 2.1: Coefficient of Performance and the Carnot efficiency of the heat pump vs Temperature lift [6].....	4
Figure 2.2: COP of the heat pump vs Source/Sink Temperature [7]	5
Figure 3.1: Overview of the methodology	6
Figure 3.2: A schematic showing the chosen system configuration	7
Figure 3.3: Duration curve for the heat demands.....	8
Figure 3.4: Schematic of the heat pump system network	10
Figure 3.5: Default characteristic curve for the isentropic efficiency of the compressor in TESPpy library	12
Figure 3.6: Heating capacity, electrical power, and COP curves of the chosen heat pump.....	13
Figure 3.7: Carnot efficiency/COP vs Temperature Lift plot for the chosen heat pump	14
Figure 3.8: Flowchart explaining the fast calculation mode of the TESPpy heat pump model	17
Figure 3.9: Schematic representation of the hot water tank model.....	18
Figure 3.10: Flow chart explaining the fast calculation mode of the PV-T system model	23
Figure 3.11: Control flow for domestic hot water demand.....	24
Figure 3.12: Control flow for space heating demand.....	25
Figure 3.13: Control strategy 1, for the operation of heat pump.....	26
Figure 3.14: Control strategy 2, for the operation of heat pump.....	27
Figure 3.15: Advanced control strategy for the operation of heat pump + PV-T collector array	28
Figure 3.16: The flow of information between the different models	29
Figure 4.1: Heat Supply/Demand Profile – Reduced Demands.....	33
Figure 4.2: Monthly Heat Supply/Demand – Reduced Demands.....	33
Figure 4.3: Comparison of the cumulative monthly heat supplied by the different heat pump models.....	34
Figure 4.4: Heat supplied by the different heat pump models – reduced demands	35
Figure 4.5: Hot water tank temperature profile for the simulations with all heat pump models– reduced demands.....	36
Figure 4.6: COP of the heat pump vs. Temperature Lift – reduced demands.....	36
Figure 4.7: COP of the heat pump vs Temperature Lift comparison with manufacturer’s curves – reduced demands.....	37
Figure 4.8: COP of the heat pump vs Condenser Water Outlet Temperature – reduced demands	38
Figure 4.9: COP of the heat pump vs Source Air Temperature – reduced demands	39
Figure 4.10: COP of the heat pump vs. Temperature Lift vs. Source Air Temperature – reduced demands	39
Figure 4.11: Heat Supplied by the heat pump – baseline scenario	42
Figure 4.12: Hot Water Tank Temperature Profile – baseline scenario.....	43
Figure 4.13: Comparison of heat supplied by the heat pump to the hot water tank for the different configurations of PV-T system	45
Figure 4.14: Comparison of the mean hot water tank temperature for the different configurations of PV-T system.....	47
Figure 4.15: Duration curve of the heat pump source air and PV-T system outlet temperatures for the different configurations of PV-T system	48
Figure 4.16: Duration curve of the COP of the heat pump for the different configurations of PV-T system	49
Figure 4.17: Comparison of the thermal energy from the PV-T system and ambient air for the different configurations of the PV-T system.....	50

Figure 4.18: Comparison of system electrical performance for the different configurations of PV-T system	52
Figure 4.19: Comparison of the PV-T system and ambient thermal energy for the different configurations of PV-T system	53
Figure 4.20: Comparison of the PV-T system and grid electrical energy for the different configurations of PV-T system	54
Figure 4.21: Comparison of the PV-T system thermal and electrical efficiency for the different configurations of PV-T system	54
Figure 4.22: Comparison of the electrical energy used from the PV/PV-T system and the grid for the different configurations of PV/PV-T system	56
Figure 4.23: Comparison of the heat supplied by the heat pump with different control strategies	57
Figure 4.24: Hot water tank temperature profiles for the simulations with different control strategies	57
Figure 4.25: Periods chosen for the weekly analysis of the system performance.....	58
Figure 4.26: Weekly performance analysis of the PV-T SAHP system	60
Figure A.1: Carnot efficiency vs Temperature lift plot – <i>tespy_1stage</i> model	68
Figure B.1: Heat Supply/Demand Profile – Full Demands.....	70
Figure B.2: Monthly Heat Supply/Demand – Full Demands.....	71
Figure B.3: Heat supplied by the different heat pump models – full demands.....	71
Figure B.4: Hot water tank temperature profile for the simulations with <i>tespy</i> model – full demands	72
Figure B.5: Hot water tank temperature profile for the simulations with <i>tespy_1stage</i> model – full demands	73
Figure B.6: Hot water tank temperature profile for the simulation with <i>hplib</i> model – full demands..	73
Figure B.7: COP of the heat pump vs. Temperature Lift – reduced demands	74
Figure B.8: COP of the heat pump vs Condenser Water Outlet Temperature – full demands	74
Figure B.9: COP of the heat pump vs Source Air Temperature – full demands.....	75
Figure B.10: COP of the heat pump vs. Temperature Lift vs. Source Air Temperature – full demands	75

List of Tables

Table 3.1: Design data for the PV-T SAHP system.....	7
Table 3.2: Nominal operating point data	12
Table 3.3: Design point conditions	13
Table 3.4: Expanded heating capacity table of the heat pump.....	15
Table 3.5: Compressor isentropic efficiency map.....	15
Table 3.6: Example of detailed calculation mode.....	16
Table 3.7: Thermal parameters of the collector	19
Table 3.8: Photovoltaic parameters of the PV-T collector.....	20
Table 3.9: Values used in the PV module temperature equation	20
Table 3.10: Scenarios simulated for the validation of the developed heat pump model.....	29
Table 3.11: KPIs to compare the performance of the system with different heat pump models	30
Table 3.12: Scenarios simulated for the PV-T SAHP system.....	31
Table 3.13: Additional KPIs to compare the performance of the system including the PV-T collector system	31
Table 4.1: System performance comparison of the heat pump models for the validation scenario with reduced demands.....	40
Table 4.2: System performance for the baseline scenario.....	44
Table 4.3: Comparison of heat supplied for the different configurations of PV-T system.....	46
Table 4.4: Comparison of the heat pump operation, source air temperature and PV-T outlet temperature for the different configurations of PV-T system.....	48
Table 4.5: Comparison of maximum COP and durations for the different configurations of PV-T system	50
Table 4.6: System performance comparison of the different configurations of PV-T collector System	52
Table 4.7: Comparison of the electrical performance of the different configurations of PV/PV-T System.....	55
Table 4.8: Maximum hot water tank temperatures for the simulations with different control strategies	58
Table 4.9: Periods chosen for the weekly analysis of the system performance	59
Table 4.10: Comparison of the duration of heat pump operation for the different control strategies...	61
Table 4.11: Comparison of the system performance for the different control strategies.....	61
Table A.1: Compressor isentropic efficiency map – <i>tespy_variable_evap_m</i> model.....	67
Table A.2: Nominal operating point data – <i>tespy_1stage</i> model	67
Table A.3: Expanded heating capacity table of the heat pump – <i>tespy_1stage</i> model	68
Table A.4: Compressor isentropic efficiency map – <i>tespy_1stage_fixed_evap_m</i> model.....	69
Table A.5: Compressor isentropic efficiency map – <i>tespy_1stage_variable_evap_m</i> model	69
Table B.1: System performance comparison of the heat pump models for the validation scenario with full demands.....	76

List of abbreviations

HP	Heat Pump
PV	Photovoltaic
PV-T	Photovoltaic Thermal
PV-T SAHP	Photovoltaic thermal solar assisted heat pump
HWT	Hot Water Tank
COP	Coefficient of Performance
SoC	State of Charge
HR	Heating Rod
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
SH	Space Heating

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Today's buildings sector accounts for almost one-third of total final energy consumption and 15% of end-use sector direct CO₂ emissions, and its share of emissions rises to around 30% if indirect emissions from the electricity and heat used in the buildings are included [1, p-147/386]. Particularly, space heating accounts for 60% of global CO₂ emissions today in the buildings sector [1, p-149/386]. For the global energy sector to achieve net zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 and limit the global temperature rise to 1.5 °C without a temperature overshoot, 100% of the new buildings should be zero-carbon-emissions ready and 85% of the existing buildings should be retrofitted to zero-carbon emissions level [1, p-38/386].

To reach such an ambitious goal, heat pumps will play a crucial role, as they provide the largest electrification opportunity in the buildings sector, displacing heating from fossil fuel boilers [1, p-42/386] and enabling a greater penetration of renewable sources in the heat supply. They are especially attractive for the one-third of the global population living in regions requiring both space heating and cooling, since reversible heat pumps can deliver both services [1, p-192/386].

Coupling the heat pumps with renewable energy sources will be critical in their decarbonization. In this context, Photovoltaic Thermal (PV-T) collectors are an interesting option, combining the production of both types of solar energy – solar heat and solar electricity – in one collector, thus reaching higher yields per area. By harnessing the abundant solar resource and combining photovoltaic electricity generation with solar thermal heat collection, PV-T systems offer a multifaceted solution to augment both the electricity and heat requirements of buildings. This is particularly important if the available roof area is limited, such as in residential and commercial buildings [2, p-23/86]. The integration of heat pumps further amplifies the efficiency and versatility of these systems, enabling them to meet the complex and variable thermal demands of residential and commercial structures.

In summary, the building sector in Germany is at the forefront of the nation's efforts to reduce energy consumption and GHG emissions. Achieving these ambitious goals necessitates innovative solutions, and PV-T Solar Assisted Heat Pump (SAHP) systems represent a promising avenue. This study seeks to contribute to the body of knowledge by evaluating the technical performance of PV-T SAHP systems, particularly regarding their application in space heating and domestic hot water production for buildings, thereby contributing to the broader discourse on energy transition and sustainable building practices.

1.2 Objectives

This master's thesis focuses on the simulation of PV-T SAHP systems tailored to the specific thermal demands of buildings, with a focus on space heating and domestic hot water production, in order to gain insights on the potential of such systems in meeting the thermal demands. The objectives of the research undertaken are:

- Identification of an appropriate configuration of a PV-T SAHP system in order to meet the building thermal demands in consideration

- Development of suitable models in order to simulate the performance of the PV-T SAHP system
- Evaluation of the technical performance of the PV-T SAHP system and the advantage of such a system as compared to a regular heat pump system
- Identification of the optimal size of the PV-T system for the building thermal demands in consideration
- Implementation of different control strategies to improve the utilization of the PV-T system, by increasing the duration of combined operation of the PV-T system and the heat pump

1.3 Structure of the report

The theory relevant to the simulation of PV-T SAHP systems is presented in section 2. The methodology undertaken for the master's thesis, from the design basis for the simulations, the development of the necessary models, and the different scenarios that are simulated, is described in detail in section 3. The results from the functional validation of the heat pump model and the system simulations are presented and discussed in section 4. The conclusion of the study and scope for future work are presented in section 5.

2 Theory

Heat pumps are becoming increasingly acknowledged as a pivotal technology in the effort to reduce carbon emissions from heating, gaining greater policy backing in numerous countries in recent years. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), heat pumps have the potential to cut global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions by at least 500 million tonnes by 2030. This reduction is equivalent to the annual CO₂ emissions produced by all the cars currently on the roads in Europe. [3]

The sale of heat pumps has seen a significant increase globally with a 11% growth in 2022, with the sale of air to water heat pumps seeing a growth of 24%. In Europe, the increase in sales has been even higher, with a growth of 40% in 2022, and the sale of air to water heat pumps in particular growing by 50%. Despite this record growth, heat pumps still meet only around 10% of the global heat need in buildings. The global heat pump stock would need to almost triple by 2030, to cover at least 20% of global heating needs, to be on track with the Net Zero Emissions by 2050 (NZE) Scenario, which represents a pathway to reduce energy emissions to zero on a net basis by 2050 in order to stabilise global average temperatures at 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels. [3]

For an increased deployment of heat pumps, in difficult market segments such as multi-family buildings, innovation in system-oriented solutions with integration of energy storage, on-site solar PV and solar thermal systems, and active control are recognized as one of the key aspects.[3]

2.1 Photovoltaic Thermal (PV-T) Solar Assisted Heat Pump (SAHP) systems

The use of photovoltaic thermal (PV-T) collectors to assist the heat pumps is expanding, due to the ability of such collectors to generate both electrical and thermal energy that can be exploited by the heat pump. While the renewable electrical energy generated can be self-consumed by the heat pump, the thermal energy can allow the heat pump to operate at higher temperatures, improving the overall system efficiency. [4]

While many factors affect the performance of the heat pump, the most important is the temperature lift, which is the temperature difference between evaporation and condensation[4]. The evaporation happens at the source temperature available inside the evaporator, and the condensation happens at the sink temperature, i.e., the temperature at the outlet of the condenser. The PV-T collector allows for heat to be supplied at a higher source temperature, allowing the heat pump to operate at a higher coefficient of performance (COP), which is the ratio of the thermal energy delivered to the electrical energy consumed by the heat pump.

The configurations of the PV-T SAHP systems are classified primarily based on the integration of the PV-T collector to the evaporator of the heat pump. In direct expansion systems, PV-T collector itself acts as the evaporator, whereas in indirect expansion systems, the PV-T collector is separated from the evaporator of the heat pump. Though the direct expansion systems, have higher efficiencies, they are more vulnerable to the variations in solar radiation, requiring complex control strategies. The indirect expansion systems allow for a lower dependence on the solar radiation and thus a more flexible operation of the system. [4]

Another key component of the PV-T SAHP system is thermal storage, with the placement of the thermal storage between the heat pump and the user increasing the self-consumption of thermal energy from the PV-T collectors, and a reduction in the on/off cycles of the heat pump.[4]

2.2 Approaches to model heat pump performance

Different kinds of approaches are available for the prediction of heat pump performance, ranging from numerical approximation approaches, usually equation-fit models, to more detailed thermodynamic approaches that are developed based on thermodynamics and fundamental heat and mass transfer relations in each component constituting the heat pump system. In the numerical approximation approaches, the heat pump is described as a black box whose operation is predicted by equations derived from its performance data. While these models are simpler, the prediction of performance is not reliable outside the data ranges used for the equations. The detailed thermodynamic approaches, usually considering the evaporator, compressor, expansion valve and the condenser as the components, are more complex, and have higher accuracy in predicting the performance of the heat pump. [5]

2.3 Heat pump performance at low temperature lifts

The operation of the PV-T system along with the heat pump, results in higher source temperatures inside the evaporator of the heat pump. Consequently, the heat pump operates at lower temperature lifts, the difference between the temperature in the condenser and the evaporator of the heat pump.

In a study on the planning and design of heat pumps for low temperature lift applications [6], the coefficient of performance (COP) and the Carnot efficiency, of a low temperature lift heat pump and a standard heat pump as function of the temperature lift are presented, as shown in figure 2.1. The Carnot efficiency is the ratio of the real COP and the ideal COP. As can be seen from the figure, the performance of the heat pump is expected to have a non-linear relationship with the temperature lift, with a higher rate of increase in the coefficient of performance (COP) of the heat pump as the temperature lift decreases. It can also be seen that at lower temperature lifts, the Carnot efficiency is lower for the heat pumps.

Figure 2.1: Coefficient of Performance and the Carnot efficiency of the heat pump vs Temperature lift [6]

In a further study on the design and simulation of heat pumps driven by small-scale turbo compressor [7], the influence of the source temperature ($T_{source,in}$) and the sink temperature ($T_{sink,out}$), on the COP of the heat pump is presented, as shown in figure 2.2. The COP of the heat pump shown in the figure are for a heating capacity (\dot{Q}_{cond}) of 4 kW. As can be seen from the figure, again the COP of the heat pump has a non-linear relationship with the source/sink temperatures, with the COP increasing at a higher rate at higher/lower source/sink temperatures, that correspond to lower temperature lifts.

Figure 2.2: COP of the heat pump vs Source/Sink Temperature [7]

3 Methodology

The primary objective of this work is to simulate the performance of a PV-T SAHP system. The basis for the scenarios simulated, i.e., the system configuration and design choices, the building thermal demands, and other input data for the simulations are detailed in section 3.1. The development and co-simulation of all the models used in this work is detailed in section 3.2. The validation procedure of the developed heat pump model is detailed in section 3.3. Finally, the different scenarios simulated are detailed in section 3.4.

Figure 3.1: Overview of the methodology

3.1 Basis for the scenario simulations

In this work, the PV-T based SAHP system is designed to meet the thermal demands of two buildings within the district heating network of the Energetisches Nachbarschaftsquartier (ENaQ) project [8]. The system configuration chosen for the work is described in section 3.1.1. The thermal demand profiles of the two buildings are described in 3.1.2. The input data necessary for the simulations is shown in section 3.1.3.

3.1.1 System configuration

The system configuration for the baseline scenario consists of an air-source heat pump, coupled with a hot water tank between the heat pump and the consumer. The proposed system schematic for the baseline scenario is shown within the dotted line box in the figure 3.2.

For the PV-T SAHP system, an indirect expansion configuration is chosen, with an air PV-T collector system added in parallel to the external air source of the baseline scenario configuration, as the heat source for the refrigerant circuit of an air-source heat pump, in order to improve the performance of the heat pump. The proposed system schematic for the PV-T SAHP system is shown in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: A schematic showing the chosen system configuration

The preliminary system design is based on the data available from the project planning data of Olegeno [9]. The peak demand of the two buildings, combining both the space heating and domestic hot water demands, is 58 kW. This peak demand value serves as the basis for the required capacity of the heat pump. The total volume of the hot water storage, for both buildings combined, is 4000L. The supply temperatures of hot water for the space heating demands and the domestic hot water demands, are 35⁰C and 40⁰C respectively. The temperature drop in the space heating circuit is 7⁰C. These values have been used to design the control strategy of the system.

Table 3.1: Design data for the PV-T SAHP system

System Design Parameter	Value	Units
Total peak heating demand	58	kW
Total volume of hot water storage	4000	Litres
Space heating supply temperature	35	⁰ C
Space heating circuit temperature drop	7	⁰ C
Domestic hot water supply temperature	40	⁰ C

The total available roof area, required for the sizing of the PV-T collector system, is ~ 642 m². This value has been obtained from a previous work within the ENaQ project [10].

3.1.2 Demands

The building thermal demand profiles are available, for the year 2020, from the ENaQ project [8]. The domestic hot water (DHW) demand, in litres of water, is available at a time resolution of 15 minutes. This DHW demand data has been converted to a time resolution of 1 minute by taking the average demand over each minute. The space heating (SH) demand, in kWh, is available at a time resolution of 15 minutes. This SH demand data has been converted to kW values at a time resolution of 1 minute by taking the average demand over each minute. The duration curves for both demands are shown in figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Duration curve for the heat demands

The peak DHW demand for a single time step is observed to be 43.4 L. The peak SH demand for a single time step is observed to be 32 kW. The total annual domestic hot water demand is 2,094,641 L (73,081 kWh) whereas the total annual space heating demand is 35,921 kWh.

3.1.3 Input data

The solar radiation incident on the PV-T collector array for the location of the buildings, Oldenburg (latitude:53.14, longitude: 8.21), for the year 2020, has been obtained from the openly available Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS) database [11]. The radiation data is available for the tilted plane at an optimized slope (42°) and azimuth (-8°) directly from the database. The air which is used as heat source for the heat pump, and as the inlet fluid for the PV-T collector system is assumed to be available at ambient temperature. The ambient temperature data for the year 2020 has been taken from the PVGIS database as well. The data from the PVGIS database, available at a time resolution of 1 hour, has been converted to a resolution of 15 minutes, to match the original resolution of the thermal demands, by linearly interpolating between the missing values, with the weather data remaining the same for each minute within the 15 minute intervals.

In the hot water tank, the domestic hot water supplied is replaced by the cold mains water. The temperature of the cold water ($T_{cold\ water}$) is assumed to follow a sinusoidal curve and is calculated using equation 3.1, for each hour of the year (HoY) [12]. The cold water temperatures are calculated for 15 minute time intervals, consistent with the original time resolution of the demands, with the temperature remaining the same for each minute within the interval.

$$T_{cold\ water} = T_{average} + T_{amplitude} * \sin\left(\frac{360 * (HoY + (273.15 - d_{off}) * 24)}{8760}\right)$$

Equation 3.1: Equation to calculate the cold-water temperature

The average annual cold water temperature ($T_{average}$) is assumed to be 10°C . The mean amplitude for the annual variation ($T_{amplitude}$) is assumed to be 4°C . The shift in the maximum temperature over the course of the year (d_{off}) is assumed to be 80 days. The obtained hourly values for the cold-water temperature are converted to a time resolution of 1 minute.

3.2 Development of the models

In order to simulate the performance of the PV-T SAHP system described in section 3.1.1 to meet the building thermal demands described in section 3.1.2, models have been developed in Python programming language, for the heat pump, the hot water tank, the PV-T collector system and for the controller. The development and functionality of heat pump model is described in section 3.2.1. The functionality of the hot water tank model is described in section 3.2.2. The development and functionality of the PV-T collector system model is described in section 3.2.3. The functionality of the collector model is described in section 3.2.4. The co-simulation of the different models used in this work is described in section 3.2.5.

3.2.1 Heat pump

The heat pump model developed for this work comprises two different ways of simulating the performance of a heat pump, both based on openly available libraries. The first model is based on the [TESPy library](#) [13], while the second is based on the [hplib library](#) [14]. In both models, a quasi-steady state modelling approach has been adopted, i.e., the conditions of the operation of the heat pump vary with each time-step and the steady state performance of the heat pump is calculated at these different conditions for each time-step.

The model based on hplib, hereafter referred as “*hplib*” model, is a parametric fit equation-based model, and thus takes a statistical approach to predict the performance of the heat pump at different operating conditions. The model based on TESPy, hereafter referred as “*tespy*” model, is more complex and considers the physical states of the fluids in the different components of the heat pump. Therefore, it offers greater flexibility than the *hplib* model in estimating the performance of the heat pump at different operating conditions.

The *hplib* and *tespy* models are based on the heat pump “ait-deutschland LW-300(L)” [15], due to its suitability for the demands described in section 3.1, due to the availability of this model in *hplib* model’s database, and due to the availability of the detailed datasheets from the manufacturer required for the *tespy* model.

The subsection 3.2.1.1 describes the functionality of the *hplib* model. The section 3.2.1.2 describes both the development and the functionality of the *tespy* model.

3.2.1.1 *hplib* model

The *hplib* model is based on hplib (“Heat Pump LIBrary”), an open-source Python library that simulates the performance heat pumps using parametric fit equations for the electric power and COP. The fit parameters are identified by applying a least square regression model on the publicly available heat pump keymark data of the European Heat Pump Association (EHPA). It is possible to simulate the performance of both air and water source heat pumps. The parameters are available for a generic heat pump of both the types, as well as specific models available in the market.

The limits on the operation of the heat pump, the supply water and source air temperature ranges available from the technical datasheets of the chosen heat pump model, have been added to the model directly available in the hplib library.

The equations 3.2 and 3.3 are the fit equations for the electric power and COP respectively. The reference values, $P_{el,ref}$ is the electrical power consumption at -7°C source temperature and 52°C supply water temperature. In both the equations, p_{1-4} are the fit parameters, T_{in} is the source inlet temperature, T_{out} is the supply water temperature, and T_{amb} is the ambient temperature.

$$P_{el} = P_{el,ref} * (p_1 * T_{in} + p_2 * T_{out} + p_3 + p_4 * T_{amb})$$

Equation 3.2: Fit equation for electric power

$$COP = p_1 * T_{in} + p_2 * T_{out} + p_3 + p_4 * T_{amb}$$

Equation 3.3: Fit equation for COP

The evaporator and condenser inlet temperatures are the inputs to the model. The model checks if they are within the operating range and ensures that the source air temperature is lower than the incoming water temperature. The model then calculates the electric power, COP, the heating capacity, and the condenser mass flow as outputs. The COP and electric power are estimated as shown in equations 3.2 and 3.3 respectively. The heating capacity is calculated from the electric power and COP. The mass flow in the condenser is calculated assuming a temperature difference of 5°C .

3.2.1.2 *tespy* model

The *tespy* model is based on TESP_y (“Thermal Engineering Systems in Python”), an open-source Python library that provides a powerful simulation package for thermal processes like power plants, district heating systems, heat pumps etc. An initial version of this model has been used in a previous work[16], and significant changes have been made for this study. The performance of the heat pump is simulated by considering the energy and mass balances in the individual “*components*” of the heat pump – condenser, evaporator, compressor, expansion valve, heat exchangers and pumps – and the state of fluids in the “*connections*” between these “*components*.” The *connections* and *components* together form a topological *network* that is represented and solved as a system of equations. The schematic of the heat pump system used in this work is shown in figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Schematic of the heat pump system network

TESPy has two modes of calculation, *design* and *offdesign*, to solve the network. The *design* mode is used to design the system and forms the first calculation of the network. While designing the plant, TESPy offers much greater detail as compared to hplib, in terms of the parametrization of the individual components, for example, the isentropic efficiency of the compressor. The *offdesign* mode is used to calculate the performance of the system if parameters deviate from the design point, for example, operation at partial loads or operation at different temperature/pressure levels. The system calculations from the *design* mode form the basis for the *offdesign* mode.

The heat pump chosen for this work is available in two system configurations, either with a one-stage compressor or a two-stage compressor. The model has been developed to simulate the performance of both configurations. The two-stage compressor configuration is referred simply as “*tespy*” model, whereas the one-stage compressor configuration is referred as “*tespy_1stage*” model. Moreover, two different approaches have been taken to model the evaporator component of the heat pump. The first approach assumes a fixed mass flow of air in the evaporator, and therefore a variable temperature difference for different operating conditions. This configuration is referred as “*fixed_evap_m*” model. The second approach assumes a constant temperature difference of 5⁰C for the air in the evaporator, and therefore a variable mass flow for different operating conditions. This configuration is referred as “*variable_evap_m*” model. As an example, the one-stage compressor configuration with fixed mass flow in the evaporator is referred as “*tespy_1stage_fixed_evap_m*” model.

The development of the model to simulate the performance of this specific heat pump is described in the steps below. The data presented below corresponds to the *tespy_fixed_evap_m* model. The data for the other configurations of the model can be seen in Appendix A.

1. Initial parametrization of the model

The tutorial provided in TESPy’s documentation for simulating heat pumps has been followed to develop the first design calculation. While the tutorial provides a detailed explanation of the complete parametrization of the model, only the most relevant parameters are discussed here.

The data obtained from the manufacturer’s datasheet corresponding to the nominal operating point is shown in table 3.2. This data has been used to set the parameters of the corresponding components and connections as described in the tutorial. Since the refrigerant R448A is not available in TESPy, R404A has been used due to the similarity in their properties [17]. TESPy uses the isentropic efficiency of the compressor to calculate the power consumption as shown in equation 3.4. Since the isentropic efficiency of the compressor is not available in the datasheet, the value has been changed on a trial-and-error basis to match the power consumption calculated by the model to that mentioned in the datasheet.

$$P = \frac{\dot{m}_{in} \cdot (h_{out,s} - h_{in})}{\eta_s}$$

Equation 3.4 – where P is the power consumption of the compressor, \dot{m}_{in} is the mass flow in the compressor, ($h_{out,s} - h_{in}$) is the enthalpy change in an isentropic compression process, η_s is the isentropic efficiency of the compressor.

Table 3.2: Nominal operating point data

Parameter	Value	Units
Condenser inlet temperature	30	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Condenser outlet temperature	35	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Source air temperature	7	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Mass flow of air in evaporator	7800	m^3/h
Heating capacity	32.5	kW
Electrical Power	8.56	kW
Refrigerant	R448A	-

2. Extension of the heating capacity table of the heat pump

The design case from the previous step can be used as the basis for *offdesign* calculations to predict the system's performance (in terms of Electrical power/COP) at different operating conditions. i.e., a different source or consumer inlet temperature. While the tutorial in TESPpy's documentation provides a detailed explanation of all the changes between the two modes of calculations, only the most relevant changes are discussed here.

The refrigerant and the mass flow of air in the evaporator remain unchanged. The source air temperature and the condenser inlet temperature are available as inputs to the model. The maximum heating capacity at a particular source air temperature is available from the datasheet. The condenser outlet temperature is not known in the off-design case, but must be predicted. In the design mode, the heating capacity and temperature difference between condenser inlet and outlet are used to calculate the mass flow in the circuit. This mass flow is used to calculate the condenser outlet temperature in the off-design mode.

In order to determine the electrical power consumption, the isentropic efficiency of the compressor is required. Since this is not available in the datasheets for the entire range of operation, the default characteristic curve available in the TESPpy library, shown in figure 3.5, is used. The x-axis is the ratio of the mass flow into the compressor in the design and off-design cases, and the y-axis is the ratio of the isentropic efficiencies in the design and off-design conditions.

Figure 3.5: Default characteristic curve for the isentropic efficiency of the compressor in TESPpy library

The default characteristic curve is generic and therefore does not accurately reflect the performance of the specific model of the heat pump chosen. Instead of relying on the isentropic efficiency from a single design point and the default characteristic curve across the entire range of operation, a series of design points have been developed based on the data available in the manufacturer’s datasheet for the operating conditions shown in table 3.3.

Table 3.3: Design point conditions

Source air temperatures	-20, -15, -12, -10, -7, -2, 2, 7, 10, 12, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35
Condenser outlet temperatures	15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55

The operating range of the heat pump for the source air temperature is -20°C to 35°C . The actual operation range of the heat pump on the condenser outlet temperature is 25°C to 60°C . In the model, the range is further increased to 15°C to 60°C , in order to simulate low temperature lift conditions. The temperature difference in the condenser, constant at 5°C in the design case, has been used to calculate the condenser inlet temperature.

The manufacturer’s datasheets contain the heating power curves and the electrical power curves as shown in figure 3.6. In all the plots, the x-axis corresponds to the source (air) temperature. The data is available for the entire range of source air temperature, but only for two condenser outlet temperatures, 35°C and 55°C .

Figure 3.6: Heating capacity, electrical power, and COP curves of the chosen heat pump

The heating capacity increases with an increase in the source air temperature, but does not change significantly with a change in the condenser outlet temperature. At a given source air temperature, the heating capacity for all the other condenser outlet temperatures is assumed to be the average of the heating capacities at 35°C and 55°C .

The power consumption changes with both the source air temperature and the condenser outlet temperature. An approach based on Carnot efficiency has been used to predict the power consumption at the condenser outlet temperatures other than 35°C and 55°C . The ideal COP is calculated, using equation 3.5, for all the operating points. For the operating points where the power consumption/COP is known, the Carnot efficiency has been

calculated using equation 3.6. The temperature lift for all the operating points is calculated using equation 3.7.

$$COP_{ideal} = \frac{T_h}{T_h - T_c}$$

Equation 3.5– where T_h is the condenser water outlet temperature, T_c is the source air temperature, and COP_{ideal} is the ideal coefficient of performance of the heat pump

$$\eta_{carnot} = \frac{COP_{real}}{COP_{ideal}}$$

Equation 3.6 – where COP_{real} is the real coefficient of performance of the heat pump, and η_{carnot} is the carnot efficiency of the heat pump

$$T_{lift} = T_h - T_c$$

Equation 3.7- T_{lift} is the temperature lift

A second order polynomial equation has been fit to the pairs of the Carnot efficiencies and the corresponding temperature lifts, of operating points with condenser outlet temperatures 35⁰C and 55⁰C, as shown in figure 3.7. In this figure, the COP of the heat pump is also plotted against the temperature lift. The trends observed for the Carnot efficiency and the COP are like the trends expected from the literature, that are shown in figure 2.1. The Carnot efficiencies of the remaining operating points are estimated using the fit equation, which in turn are used to estimate the real COP/power consumption.

Figure 3.7: Carnot efficiency/COP vs Temperature Lift plot for the chosen heat pump

For the series of design points in table 3.3, the calculated heating capacity and power consumption data is summarized in table 3.4

Table 3.4: Expanded heating capacity table of the heat pump

Source air temperature (deg. C)	Heating Capacity (kW) / Power Consumption (kW)									
	Condenser outlet temperature (deg. C)									
	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60
-20	15.8 / 5.27	15.8 / 5.72	15.8 / 6.26	15.8 / 6.92	15.8 / 8.6	15.8 / 8.9	15.8 / 10.45	-	-	-
-15	19 / 5.78	19 / 6.23	19 / 6.76	19 / 7.4	19 / 8.65	19 / 9.2	19 / 10.53	-	-	-
-12	21 / 6.06	21 / 6.51	21 / 7.04	21 / 7.66	21 / 8.7	21 / 9.37	21 / 10.6	-	-	-
-10	22.3 / 6.21	22.3 / 6.67	22.3 / 7.19	22.3 / 7.8	22.3 / 8.75	22.3 / 9.46	22.3 / 10.63	22.3 / 12.17	-	-
-7	24.28 / 6.42	24.28 / 6.88	24.28 / 7.4	24.28 / 8	24.28 / 8.75	24.28 / 9.58	24.28 / 10.67	24.28 / 12.07	24.28 / 12.9	-
-2	27.1 / 6.55	27.1 / 7.04	27.1 / 7.55	27.1 / 8.13	27.2 / 8.75	27.1 / 9.57	27.1 / 10.53	27.1 / 11.72	27 / 12.8	27.1 / 15.34
2	29.39 / 6.57	29.39 / 7.11	29.39 / 7.64	29.39 / 8.2	29.67 / 8.7	29.39 / 9.56	29.39 / 10.44	29.39 / 11.51	29.1 / 12.8	29.39 / 14.6
7	33.25 / 6.55	33.25 / 7.31	33.25 / 7.91	33.25 / 8.5	32.5 / 8.55	33.25 / 9.83	33.25 / 10.65	33.25 / 11.63	34 / 12.8	33.25 / 14.32
10	38.47 / 6.66	38.47 / 7.89	38.47 / 8.65	38.47 / 9.33	39.43 / 9.35	38.47 / 10.77	38.47 / 11.62	38.47 / 12.63	37.5 / 13.4	38.47 / 15.34
12	40.5 / 5.91	40.5 / 7.84	40.5 / 8.75	40.5 / 9.48	40.5 / 9.4	40.5 / 10.94	40.5 / 11.79	40.5 / 12.77	40.5 / 13.5	40.5 / 15.38
15	-	42.4 / 7.21	42.4 / 8.55	42.4 / 9.38	42.4 / 9.4	42.4 / 10.86	42.4 / 11.68	42.4 / 12.61	42.4 / 13.5	42.4 / 15.03
20	-	-	45.1 / 7.54	45.1 / 8.94	45.1 / 9.4	45.1 / 10.59	45.1 / 11.37	45.1 / 12.23	45.1 / 13.5	45.1 / 14.36
25	-	-	-	48 / 7.9	48 / 9.4	48 / 10.28	48 / 11.09	48 / 11.92	48 / 13.6	48 / 13.85
30	-	-	-	-	51 / 9.4	51 / 9.79	51 / 10.75	51 / 11.6	51 / 13.7	51 / 13.42
35	-	-	-	-	-	54 / 8.6	54 / 10.2	54 / 11.21	54 / 13.75	54 / 13

3. Generating the compressor efficiency map

The model is parametrized for each of the design point in table 3.4, as done for the initial parametrization of the model for the nominal operating point. As shown in equation 3.4, the power consumption of the compressor is dependent on the isentropic efficiency, which is set as a parameter in the compressor. It is changed for each point in order to match the power consumption calculated by the model and that in the table. The isentropic efficiency values are restricted to the range of 0.25 - 0.95. In the instances when the power values cannot be matched even at the extreme values, they are assumed despite the difference in power predicted by the model and that in the table 3.4. The compressor isentropic efficiency map generated as described is summarized in table 3.5.

Table 3.5: Compressor isentropic efficiency map

Source air temperature (deg. C)	Compressor Isentropic Efficiency									
	Condenser outlet temperature (deg. C)									
	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60
-20	0.54	0.55	0.55	0.54	0.41	0.43	0.34	-	-	-
-15	0.55	0.57	0.58	0.58	0.51	0.53	0.47	-	-	-
-12	0.55	0.57	0.59	0.60	0.57	0.57	0.53	-	-	-
-10	0.55	0.57	0.60	0.61	0.59	0.60	0.57	0.51	-	-
-7	0.54	0.57	0.60	0.62	0.63	0.63	0.62	0.58	0.61	-
-2	0.53	0.57	0.60	0.63	0.67	0.67	0.68	0.67	0.68	0.59
2	0.51	0.56	0.60	0.64	0.69	0.70	0.71	0.72	0.71	0.71
7	0.52	0.55	0.59	0.64	0.71	0.72	0.75	0.78	0.84	0.83
10	0.57	0.57	0.60	0.65	0.79	0.74	0.78	0.82	0.86	0.90
12	0.66	0.58	0.61	0.65	0.78	0.75	0.79	0.84	0.93	0.94
15	-	0.61	0.61	0.65	0.77	0.75	0.80	0.85	0.93	0.95
20	-	-	0.65	0.64	0.72	0.74	0.80	0.86	0.91	0.95
25	-	-	-	0.69	0.68	0.73	0.79	0.86	0.87	0.95
30	-	-	-	-	0.62	0.73	0.78	0.86	0.83	0.95
35	-	-	-	-	-	0.79	0.78	0.85	0.79	0.95

Detailed calculation mode of the model for the simulations

After establishing a series of design points, the model has then been developed to estimate the performance of the heat pump at any operating point within its range. The heat pump is used as the primary heating source for the hot water tank. The temperature of the water flow to the heat pump from the hot water tank, and the source air temperature are the required inputs.

The model checks if the conditions are within the operation range of the heat pump and ensures that the source air temperature is lower than the incoming water temperature. The source air temperature closest to the input value is then identified from the table 3.4. The model checks that the inlet water temperature is lower than the maximum possible condenser outlet temperature at the identified design source air temperature. Assuming a temperature difference of 5⁰C in the condenser in the design case, an initial condenser outlet temperature is estimated. The closest design point to the estimated condenser outlet temperature is then identified from the table 3.4. In case this estimated condenser temperature is greater than the maximum possible outlet temperature, the maximum value is used as the design point. The heating capacity and the isentropic efficiency of the compressor corresponding to the design point source air and condenser outlet water temperatures are identified from table 3.4 and table 3.5 respectively.

The model first performs a network calculation in the design mode at the identified design point operating conditions. An offdesign mode calculation of the network is then performed for the actual input operating conditions, based in the design mode calculation and the default characteristics of TESPy, to obtain the condenser outlet water temperature (supply temperature), the mass flow of water in the condenser and the power consumption of the heat pump.

Table 3.6: Example of detailed calculation mode

Inputs		Design Point Data			
Source air temperature	Condenser water inlet temperature	Source air temperature	Condenser water outlet temperature	Heat load	Compressor isentropic efficiency
3	32	2	35	29.67	0.65
18	48	20	55	45.1	0.91

Fast calculation mode of the model

In addition to the detailed mode of calculation explained above, a fast calculation mode has also been implemented in the model to improve its computational speed. The model is discreetly parametrized over the entire operation range of the heat pump, at a resolution of 1⁰C for both the inputs, the source air temperature, and the condenser water inlet temperature. The detailed calculation mode has been implemented over this range of inputs and the output data from the model- the coefficient of performance (COP) of the heat pump and the condenser mass flow rate- have been saved. During the simulation, the saved inputs that are lower/closest to the actual input data are identified, and the saved output data for these points are used to calculate the outputs of the model, rather than performing the actual design and off-design calculations. Though the granularity of the model is reduced, there is a significant improvement in the simulation duration.

Figure 3.8: Flowchart explaining the fast calculation mode of the TESP heat pump model

3.2.2 Hot water tank

The hot water tank model developed for another project [18], is used in this work to act as a buffer in between the heating device and the heat consumer. It is a multinode stratified thermal tank model [19], where the tank volume is divided into a specified number of layers (nodes) of equal volume, each characterized by a specific temperature. A traditional density distribution approach is adopted where the water flowing into the tank enters the layer that best matches its density (i.e., temperature). The model assumes that the fluid streams are fully mixed before leaving each of the layers and the flows between the layers follow the law of mass conservation. Heat transfer to the surrounding environment from the walls of the tank, and the heat transfer between the layers have been considered.

3.2.2.1 Parametrization of the model

The schematic of the hot water tank model is shown in figure 3.9. The dimensions of the tank are specified in terms of its volume and height. As mentioned in section 3.1.1, the storage volume required is 4000L. The height of the tank is calculated assuming a height to diameter ratio of 3:1. After reviewing the literature for the optimum number of nodes in the tank [19], especially its impact on long term simulations [20], parametrizing the tank to contain six layers seemed reasonable. Each layer is in turn parametrized with a sensor in the model to record its temperature. The initial temperature of all the layers at the beginning of the simulation is set to 20°C.

The flows into and out of the tank are specified as the connections of the hot water tank model. The flow going to the heat pump (HP_out), the space heating demand (SH_out), and the domestic hot water demand (DHW_out) are connected to the bottom layer, the fourth layer and the top layer respectively. As described above, the flows coming into the tank are not connected to a fixed layer in the tank. They are connected to the layer with a temperature closest to that of the flow.

Figure 3.9: Schematic representation of the hot water tank model

The heat transfer coefficient of the walls of the tank (htc_{walls}) is assumed to be $0.28 \text{ W/m}^2\text{-K}$ [7, page 117]. The heat transfer coefficient for the heat transfer between the layers of the tank is assumed to be 1.5 times the thermal conductivity of water [7, page 82]. The value is calculated as 0.897 W/m-K , considering the thermal conductivity of water to be 0.598 W/m-K [21].

3.2.2.2 Calculation of the model

The initial temperature profile inside the tank can be specified at the time of initialization of the model. For flows coming into the tank, both the temperature and flow rate should be specified. For the flows going out of the tank, only the flow rate should be specified, as the temperature is obtained from the corresponding layer of the tank. The model ensures that the overall flow into and out of the tank is equal. The model then updates the temperatures of each layer based on the water flows through the specified connections, the heat transfer between the layers and the heat transfer to the surrounding environment. The model has the functionality to flip the layers to ensure a negative temperature gradient from the top to the bottom of the tank. Finally, the model updates the connections with respect to the updated layer temperatures. For the flows going out of the tank, the temperature is updated. For the flows coming into the tank, the corresponding layer is updated.

3.2.3 Photovoltaic-Thermal (PV-T) collector system

The photovoltaic-thermal (PV-T) collector system model used in this work has been developed as a combination of two separate models for the thermal and photovoltaic components of the collector. The thermal performance of the PV-T collector has been modelled based on the openly available TESPpy library [13]. As is the case in the heat pump model, a quasi-steady state modelling approach is adopted, i.e., the conditions of the operation of the PV-T collector vary with each time-step and the steady state performance of the PV-T collector is calculated at these different conditions for each time-step. The photovoltaic performance of the PV-T collector has been modelled in a simple manner as a standalone photovoltaic panel, again using a quasi-steady state approach and the considering just the effect of panel temperature on its efficiency.

3.2.3.1 Modelling the thermal performance

The solar collector *component* available in TESPpy has been used to model the thermal performance of the PV-T collector. The collector *component* and the corresponding inlet and outlet *connections* form a simple topological network that is solved by TESPpy. The operating fluid and its mass flow (\dot{m}) are specified as parameters for the *connections*. For the collector *components*, the area (A), the optical efficiency (η_{opt}), the linear thermal loss coefficient (α_1) and the quadratic thermal loss coefficient (α_2) are specified as parameters. As mentioned in section 3.1.1, an air collector is used, in order to operate it along with the air source heat pump. The relevant parameters have been obtained from literature for a reference glazed type PV-T air collector [22], and are summarized in table 3.7.

Table 3.7: Thermal parameters of the collector

Parameter	Value	Units
Operating fluid	Air	
\dot{m}	0.02	kg/s
A	0.4	m ²
η_{opt}	0.364	-
α_1	4.79	W/K-m ²
α_2	0	W/K ² -m ²

The equations for steady state energy balance, equations 3.8, 3.9 and 3.10, are applied to each collector panel, with the inlet temperature (T_{in}) and the ambient temperature (T_{amb}) and the tilted plane irradiance (E) being provided as inputs, to calculate the temperature of the fluid in the outlet *connection* (T_{out}) and the thermal power of the collector *component* (Q)

$$\dot{m} * (h_{out} - h_{in}) = A * (E * \eta_{opt} - \alpha_1 * (T_m - T_{amb}) - \alpha_2 * (T_m - T_{amb})^2)$$

Equation 3.8: Energy balance equation for the collector, where ($h_{out} - h_{in}$) is the enthalpy change of the fluid in the collector, T_m is the mean temperature of the fluid in the collector

$$T_m = \frac{T_{out} + T_{in}}{2}$$

Equation 3.9: Equation for the mean temperature of the fluid in the collector

$$Q = \dot{m} * (h_{out} - h_{in})$$

Equation 3.10: Equation for the thermal power of the collector

3.2.3.2 Modelling the photovoltaic performance

The photovoltaic performance of the PV-T collector is modelled by calculating the electrical power output of the PV module (P), as shown in equation 3.11. The PV module area (A) is the same as for the thermal collector mentioned in table 3.7. The tilted plane irradiance (E) is provided as an input.

$$P = \eta_{el} * E * A$$

Equation 3.11: Electrical power of the collector

$$\eta_{el} = \eta_{el,ref} * (1 - \beta_0 * (T_{PV} - 25))$$

Equation 3.12: Temperature dependence of the electrical efficiency of the collector

The electrical efficiency (η_{el}) of the collector varies with the temperature of the PV module (T_{PV}) and is calculated as shown in equation 3.12. The reference electrical efficiency ($\eta_{el,ref}$) at standard test conditions (STC - 25°C) and the temperature coefficient (β_0) are specified as a parameters. The relevant parameters have been obtained from literature for a reference glazed type PV-T air collector [22], and are summarized in table 3.8.

Table 3.8: Photovoltaic parameters of the PV-T collector

Parameter	Value	Units
$\eta_{el,ref}$	0.13	-
β_0	0.006	1/K

When the thermal component of the PV-T collector is operated, to supply air to the heat pump, the temperature of the PV module is assumed to be the mean temperature of the air inside the collector [23], as calculated by equation 3.9. However, when the thermal component of the PV-T collector is not operated, in the cases when the heat pump is turned off, the temperature of the PV module is calculated using the photovoltaic cell temperature equation available in the HOMER simulation software [24], as shown in equation 3.13.

$$T_{PV} = \frac{T_{amb} + (T_{PV,NOCT} - T_{amb,NOCT}) * \left(\frac{E}{E_{NOCT}}\right) * \left(1 - \frac{\eta_{el,ref} * (1 - \beta_0 * T_{PV,ref})}{\tau\alpha}\right)}{1 + (T_{PV,NOCT} - T_{amb,NOCT}) * \left(\frac{E}{E_{NOCT}}\right) * \left(\frac{\beta_0 * T_{PV,ref}}{\tau\alpha}\right)}$$

Equation 3.13: Equation for the PV module temperature

In the equation 3.13, $T_{PV,NOCT}$ is the nominal operating cell (PV module) temperature (NOCT), $T_{amb,NOCT}$ is the ambient temperature at which the NOCT is defined, E_{NOCT} is the tilted plane irradiance at which NOCT is defined, $T_{PV,ref}$ is the PV module temperature at the reference STC conditions, τ is the solar transmittance of the PV module and α is the solar absorptance of the PV module. The values for these have been obtained from literature for a reference glazed type PV-T air collector [9], and are summarized in table 3.9. All the temperatures are converted to the Kelvin scale before being used in the equation.

Table 3.9: Values used in the PV module temperature equation

Parameter	Value	Units
$T_{PV,NOCT}$	43	°C
$T_{amb,NOCT}$	20	°C
E_{NOCT}	800	W/m ²
$T_{PV,ref}$	25	°C
$\tau\alpha$	0.83	-

3.2.3.3 Configuration of the PV-T array

In addition to the parameters mentioned in the sections on thermal and photovoltaic modelling, the number of PV-T collector panels in series (n_{ser}) and in parallel (n_{par}) must be specified to complete the parametrization of the model.

The number of PV-T collector panels in parallel are calculated considering the need to maintain a fixed mass flow rate within each panel and to supply the required mass flow of air to the heat pump. The mass flow of air to the heat pump is 7800 m³/h (from table 3.2), or 2.65 kg/s assuming an air density of 1.225 kg/m³ [25]. The mass flow rate of air in each panel is 0.02 kg/s (from table 3.7). The number of panels in parallel is calculated to be 133.

With a fixed number of PV-T collector panels in parallel, the number of panels in series are limited by the building roof area available which is 642 m², as mentioned in section 3.1.1. The maximum number of panels in series are calculated, using a panel area of 0.4 m² (from table 3.7), to be 12.

In the simulations, multiple configurations are analyzed, with the number of PV-T collector panels in parallel fixed at 133 and the number of panels in series varying between 1 and 12.

3.2.3.4 Calculation of the model

An approach like that taken in the TESPy heat pump model has been taken to model the PV-T system. A detailed calculation mode has first been implemented to solve for the varying input conditions using TESPy. Later, a fast calculation mode has been added to use pre-calculated model outputs in order to improve the computational performance of the model.

Detailed calculation mode of the model

A TESPy *network* with the specified number of solar collector *components* in series, with the corresponding inlet and outlet *connections* is parametrized with the values from table 3.6. The ambient temperature (T_{amb}), the tilted plane irradiance (E), and the temperature of air at the inlet of the system (T_{in} , same as T_{amb}) are available as inputs. The TESPy network is solved in the design mode for these inputs.

The total thermal power of the system is calculated by adding the thermal powers of each panel in series and then multiplying this value by the number of panels in parallel, as shown in equation 3.14. The thermal efficiency of the system is calculated from the total thermal power and the total incident irradiation as shown in equation 3.15.

$$Total\ thermal\ power = \left(\sum_1^{n_{ser}} Thermal\ power\ i \right) * n_{par}$$

Equation 3.14: Thermal power of the PV-T system, where Thermal Power i is the thermal power of the i^{th} panel in series

$$\eta_{thermal} = \frac{Total\ thermal\ power}{E * A * n_{ser} * n_{par}}$$

Equation 3.15: Thermal efficiency of the PV-T system, where $\eta_{thermal}$ is the thermal efficiency

The electric power of the system is calculated in two different ways, depending on the operation of the PV-T system, as explained in the section 3.2.3.2. When the PV-T system is running, and therefore supplying the air to the heat pump, the total electric power is calculated, as shown in equation 3.16, by multiplying the sum of the electric power of the panels in series with the number of panels in parallel. For each panel in series, the mean temperature of the fluid in the collector is different and therefore the electric power generated is different.

$$Total\ electric\ power = \left(\sum_1^{n_{ser}} Electric\ power\ i \right) * n_{par}$$

Equation 3.16: Electric power of the PV-T system when it is on, where Electric Power i is the electric power of the i^{th} panel in series

When the PV-T system is off, the total electric power is calculated, as shown in equation 3.17, by multiplying the electric power generated by a single panel with the total number of panels. In this case, the power generated by each panel is the same as the PV module temperature is the same for all the panels.

$$Total\ electric\ power = Electric\ power_i * n_{par} * n_{ser}$$

Equation 3.17: Electric power of the PV-T system when it is on, where Electric Power i is the electric power of any one panel

The electrical efficiency of the system is calculated from the total electric power and the total incident irradiation as shown in equation 3.18.

$$\eta_{electrical} = \frac{Total\ electric\ power}{E * A * n_{ser} * n_{par}}$$

Equation 3.18: Thermal efficiency of the PV-T system, where $\eta_{thermal}$ is the thermal efficiency

The temperature of air in the final outlet *connection* (T_{out}), is obtained from the network as an output. A mixing strategy has been implemented to ensure that the air being supplied by the PV-T system is within the limits of operation of the heat pump. The temperature of the source air in the heat pump should be lower than the maximum temperature limit (35°C, from section 3.2.1.2) and the condenser inlet water temperature of the heat pump. In case the outlet temperature of air from the PV-T system is higher than either of these, the outlet air is mixed with ambient air to bring down the temperature to the lower value of the two (T_{limit}). The energy lost in this process is calculated, assuming a value of 1006 J/kg-K for the specific heat capacity of air ($C_{p, air}$) [26] as shown in equation 3.19.

$$Thermal\ power\ lost = Total\ mass\ flow\ of\ air * C_{p,air} * (T_{out} - T_{limit})$$

Equation 3.19: Thermal power lost due to mixing

Fast calculation mode of the model

For the different configurations of the PV-T system, with the panels in series ranging from 1 to 12, the detailed calculations are performed beforehand for the whole year with the ambient temperature and the titled plane irradiance as inputs, without applying any mixing strategy. The outlet temperature of air from the PV-T system, the total thermal power, the total electric power, the thermal and electrical efficiencies, are obtained as outputs from the system and are

saved. During the simulation the saved outputs for each time step are retrieved and used, instead of performing the detailed calculation in real-time. The mixing strategy is then implemented on the outlet temperature retrieved from the saved data.

The total electric power that is obtained from the saved data, is that calculated assuming the PV-T system to be running. Since the thermal part of the PV-T system is operated only when the heat pump is on, during the simulation, the electric power is corrected for the time steps when the heat pump is off, by replacing it with the electric power of only the PV modules.

Figure 3.10: Flow chart explaining the fast calculation mode of the PV-T system model

3.2.4 Controller

The controller model used in this work utilizes simple Boolean logic to:

1. Match the heating demands with the supply from the hot water tank/back up heaters
2. Control the operation of the heat pump
3. Adapt the control strategy during the photovoltaic-thermal (PV-T) collector operation

In order to perform each of the above functions, the controller must be initialized with a set of parameters. The controller then analyzes the information received from the different models and sends the necessary information back to the models for the progression of the simulation. The specific parameters and the information exchange for each of the functions are detailed below.

3.2.4.1 Domestic hot water demand

The controller is initialized with a set point of 40°C for the domestic hot water (DHW) supply temperature ($T_{hr_sp_dhw}$). For each time step of the simulation, the controller receives the domestic hot water demand (dhw_demand), in liters of water, the temperature of the water available for supply from the hot water tank (dhw_out_T), and the temperature of the cold inlet water (dhw_in_T). The controller then calculates the flow rate of water to be supplied from the tank by dividing the demand with the time step (dhw_out_F). If the water from the tank is available for supply at a temperature greater than the set point, flow is adjusted by mixing with the cold inlet water. If the temperature of water from tank is lower than the set point, the controller calculates the heat to be supplied by the backup heater to achieve the set point temperature, which is also the electric power required (P_{hr_dhw}) by the heater, assuming 100% efficiency. Finally, the controller sets the information of the flows to the hot water tank (dhw_out_F , dhw_in_F).

Figure 3.11: Control flow for domestic hot water demand

3.2.4.2 Space heating demand

The controller is initialized with the set points of 35⁰C for the space heating (SH) supply temperature ($T_{hr_sp_sh}$) and 7⁰C for the temperature difference in the space heating circuit (sh_dT). For each time step of the simulation, the controller receives the space heating demand (sh_demand), in kW, the temperature of the water available for supply from the hot water tank (sh_out_T). The controller then calculates the flow rate of water to be supplied from the tank from the demand and the temperature difference (sh_in_F). If the water from the tank is available for supply at a temperature greater than the set point, the return temperature (sh_in_T) is calculated as the difference between the supply temperature and the temperature difference. If the temperature of water from tank is lower than the set point, the controller calculates the heat to be supplied by the backup heater to achieve the set point temperature, which is also the electric power required (P_{hr_sh}) by the heater, assuming 100% efficiency. The controller also calculates the return temperature as the difference between the set point temperature and the temperature difference. Finally, the controller sets the information of the flows to the hot water tank (sh_out_F , sh_in_F , sh_in_T).

Figure 3.12: Control flow for space heating demand

3.2.4.3 Heat pump operation -control strategy 1

A simple hysteresis control based on the temperature of the bottom layer of the hot water tank has been implemented for the operation of the heat pump. The controller is initialized with a higher ($T_{hp_sp_h}$) and lower ($T_{hp_sp_l}$) temperature set point for the hot water tank. The controller then receives the temperature of the bottom layer ($bottom_layer_T$) of the hot water tank. The bottom layer of the tank is controlled to be maintained in between the two temperature limits, i.e., the heat pump is turned on when the temperature in the bottom layer of the tank falls below the lower set point. The heat pump is turned off only when the temperature in the bottom layer of the tank is greater than the higher set point. The heat pump continues to remain turned off and turns back on only when the temperature of the bottom layer falls below the lower set point again. The heat pump is controlled by setting its status (hp_status) to either 'on' or 'off' based on the control logic explained above.

Figure 3.13: Control strategy 1, for the operation of heat pump

3.2.4.4 Heat pump operation -control strategy 2

In addition to the control strategy for the heat pump operation explained in section 3.2.4.3, which is based only on the temperature of the bottom layer of the hot water tank, a control strategy based on the temperatures of both the bottom and top layers of the tank has been implemented. The fifth layer of the hot water tank is considered as the top layer instead of the sixth layer, in order to ensure a higher temperature in the actual top layer for periods of high demands. The controller is initialized with a higher ($T_{hp_sp_h}$) and lower ($T_{hp_sp_l}$) temperature set point for the hot water tank, as done in the first control strategy. The controller then receives the temperatures of the top layer (top_layer_T) and the bottom layer ($bottom_layer_T$) of the hot water tank. The top layer of the tank is controlled against the higher set point, i.e., the heat pump is turned on when the temperature in the top layer of the tank falls below the higher set point. The bottom layer of the tank is controlled against the lower set point, i.e., the heat pump is turned off only when the temperature in the bottom layer of the tank is greater than the lower set point. In this case, the temperature of the top layer is expected to be greater than the higher set point due to stratification inside the tank. The heat pump

continues to remain turned off and turns back on only when the temperature of the top layer falls below the higher set point again. The heat pump is controlled by setting its status (*hp_status*) to either 'on' or 'off' based on the control logic explained above.

Figure 3.14: Control strategy 2, for the operation of heat pump

3.2.4.5 Advanced control strategy for PV-T collector operation

When operating the photovoltaic-thermal (PV-T) collector along with the heat pump, an advanced control strategy has been implemented in an attempt to extend the operation of the heat pump during the day time when the source air for the heat pump is available at a higher temperature. The controller receives the inlet (PVT_T_{in}) and the outlet (PVT_T_{out}) temperatures of air in the PV-T collector array, and calculates the temperature difference (ΔT). The set points for the heat pump operation ($T_{hp_sp_h_0}$ and $T_{hp_sp_l_0}$) are increased by the value of the temperature difference (ΔT), to increase the time of operation of the heat pump during the daytime when the ΔT is high. The value of ΔT is restricted to a maximum of 7°C , in order to not heat up the tank much higher than the required 40°C ($T_{hr_sp_dhw}$) for the domestic hot water supply.

The control logic explained in section 3.2.4.4 has been modified to ensure that the bottom layer in the tank is sufficiently hot, even in the cases where the top layer of the tank is above its

temperature limit. An additional check has been implemented to keep the heat pump on, when the temperature of bottom layer of the tank ($bottom_layer_T$) is below the lower temperature set point ($T_{hp_sp_l}$), despite the temperature of the top layer (top_layer_T) being higher than the higher set point ($T_{hp_sp_h}$). The remaining control flow is like that explained in section 3.2.4.4.

Figure 3.15: Advanced control strategy for the operation of heat pump + PV-T collector array

3.2.5 Co-simulation

The stand-alone models for heat pump, hot water tank, photovoltaic thermal (PV-T) system and controller are dependent on the information from each other that only becomes available over the course of the simulation, as shown in figure 3.16. This type of joint simulation of models is called co-simulation. In this work, the co-simulation software mosaik [27] has been used to handle the flow of information between the different models. The input data for all the models is handled by mosaik-csv [28], a tool available in mosaik that operates as a pseudo

simulator for the input data available in a CSV (comma separated values) data format. The outputs from the simulation are saved using `mosaik-hdf5` [29], a tool available in `mosaik` to save the output data from the models in a HDF5 (Hierarchical Data Format version 5) database.

Figure 3.16: The flow of information between the different models

The co-simulation of all the models is done at a time step of 1 minute, with the information being exchanged between all the models after each time step of the simulation.

The heat pump, hot water tank and controller models, along with the scripts to integrate them into the `mosaik` ecosystem and the scripts to simulate an example scenario, are available in the `mosaik-heatpump` library [30].

3.3 Validation of the heat pump model

The heat pump model based on `TESPy`, developed for this work, has been validated by comparing its performance with that of the `hplib` model, in meeting the building thermal demands described in section 3.1.2. The baseline scenario system configuration described in section 3.1.1, has been simulated, by considering only the external air as the heat source for the heat pump, without including the PV-T collector system. The heat pump operation is controlled, as described in section 3.2.4.3, with a higher set point of 50°C and a lower set point of 40°C for the bottom layer of the hot water tank. Both the `tespy` and the `tespy_1stage` models are validated against the `hplib` model. Moreover, both the `fixed_evap_m` and the `variable_evap_m` configurations of the `tespy` and `tespy_1stage` models are compared to check the robustness of the developed models. Since the maximum heating capacity of the heat pump on the `tespy` model is higher than that of the `tespy_1stage` and the `hplib` models, an additional comparison of the models has been done by reducing the building thermal demands by a factor of three, and simulating the system for these reduced demands. All the scenarios simulated for the purpose of validation are summarized in the table 3.10.

Table 3.10: Scenarios simulated for the validation of the developed heat pump model

Heat Pump Model	Model Configurations	Demands	Control strategy
<i>hplib</i>	-	Full demands	Control strategy 1 for heat pump operation $T_{hp_sp_h} = 50^{\circ}\text{C}$ $T_{hp_sp_l} = 40^{\circ}\text{C}$
		Reduced Demands (1/3)	
<i>tespy</i>	<i>fixed_evap_m</i> <i>variable_evap_m</i>	Full demands	
		Reduced Demands (1/3)	
<i>tespy_1stage</i>	<i>fixed_evap_m</i> <i>variable_evap_m</i>	Full demands	
		Reduced Demands (1/3)	

A set of key performance indicators (KPIs) have been identified to compare the performance of the different heat pump models in consideration, as summarized in table 3.11.

Table 3.11: KPIs to compare the performance of the system with different heat pump models

KPI	Description	Unit
Total Electrical Energy	The total electrical energy consumed by the system, including the heat pump and the backup heaters for space heating and domestic hot water supply	kWh
HP Electrical Energy	The electrical energy consumed by the heat pump	kWh
Total Thermal Energy	The total thermal energy supplied by the system, including the heat pump and the backup heaters for space heating and domestic hot water supply	kWh
HP Thermal Energy	The thermal energy supplied by the heat pump	kWh
HR SH Energy	The thermal energy supplied, also the electrical energy consumed, by the backup heater for space heating water supply	kWh
HR DHW Energy	The thermal energy supplied, also the electrical energy consumed, by the backup heater for domestic hot water supply	kWh
HP Startups	The number of times the heat pump is turned on/off during the simulation	-
HR SH Startups	The number of times the backup heater for space heating water supply is turned on/off during the simulation	-
HR DHW Startups	The number of times the backup heater for domestic hot water supply is turned on/off during the simulation	-
Average SoC	The average temperature of the water in the hot water tank, over the entire simulation	°C
Average COP	The average coefficient of performance (COP) of the heat pump, over the entire simulation, calculated by dividing HP Thermal Energy with HP Electrical Energy	-

3.4 PV-T SAHP system simulations

The *tespy* model has been used for the simulations of the PV-T SAHP system configuration, as described in section 3.1.1, to meet the building thermal demands described in section 3.1.2. The *fixed_evap_m* configuration of the *tespy* model has been used in the simulations, with the PV-T collector system configured to supply the required mass flow of air to the heat pump.

A baseline simulation is performed initially, with only the external air acting as the heat source for the heat pump, without considering the PV-T collector system. The system simulations are later performed for different configurations of the PV-T collector system, with 2,4,6,8, 10 and 12 PV-T collector panels connected in series. In each of these cases, the number of PV-T collector panels connected in parallel are 133, in order to supply the required fixed mass flow of air to the heat pump, as explained in section 3.2.3.3. The operation of the heat pump in all the cases, is controlled as described in section 3.2.4.4, with a set point of 43°C for the top layer of the hot water tank and a set point of 37°C for the bottom layer of the hot water tank. Additionally, the performance of only the PV part of the PV-T collector system has been simulated for all the configurations of the PV-T collector system, in order to assess the relative benefit of the PV-T collector system when compared to only the PV system. Finally, the PV-T collector system configuration that is most appropriate for the building thermal demands in consideration is identified and simulated with the advanced control strategy described in

section 3.2.4.5. The different scenarios of the PV-T SAHP system that are simulated are summarized in table 3.12.

Table 3.12: Scenarios simulated for the PV-T SAHP system

Scenario	Model Configurations	Demands	Control Strategy
Baseline	Heat Pump <i>-tespy_fixed_evap_m</i> model	Full demands	Control strategy 2 for heat pump operation $T_{hp_sp_h} = 43^{\circ}\text{C}$ $T_{hp_sp_l} = 37^{\circ}\text{C}$
	No PV-T collector system		
Heat Pump + PV-T Collector system	Heat Pump <i>-tespy_fixed_evap_m</i> model	Full demands	
	PV-T collector system – n_{par} : 133 n_{ser} : 2,4,6,8,10 & 12		
Heat Pump + PV system	Heat Pump <i>-tespy_fixed_evap_m</i> model	Full demands	
	Only PV system – n_{par} : 133 n_{ser} : 2,4,6,8,10 & 12		
Heat Pump + PV-T Collector system + Advanced control strategy	Heat Pump <i>-tespy_fixed_evap_m</i> model	Full demands	Advanced control strategy $T_{hp_sp_h_0} = 43^{\circ}\text{C}$ $T_{hp_sp_l_0} = 37^{\circ}\text{C}$
	Most appropriate PV-T System configuration for the demands		

In addition to the KPIs of the system shown in table 3.11, KPIs specific to the PV-T collector system have been identified, as summarized in table 3.13, to compare the performance of the different configurations of the PV-T SAHP system.

Table 3.13: Additional KPIs to compare the performance of the system including the PV-T collector system

KPI	Description	Unit
PV-T Total Thermal Energy	The total thermal energy generated by the PV-T collector system	kWh
PV-T Thermal Energy Used	The thermal energy generated by the PV-T collector system, that is used by the heat pump	kWh
PV-T Excess Thermal Energy	The thermal energy generated by the PV-T system, that is not used by the heat pump	kWh
Ambient Thermal Energy Used	The thermal energy available from the external air, that is used by the heat pump	kWh
PV-T Total Electrical Energy	The total electrical energy generated by the PV-T collector system	kWh
PV-T Electrical Energy Used	The electrical energy generated by the PV-T collector system, that is used by the heat pump	kWh
PV-T Excess Electrical Energy	The electrical energy generated by the PV-T system, that is not used by the heat pump	kWh
Grid Electrical Energy Used	The electrical energy available from the electricity grid, that is used by the heat pump	kWh
PV-T Thermal Efficiency	The average thermal efficiency of the PV-T collector system, over the entire simulation	-
PV-T Electrical Efficiency	The average electrical efficiency of the PV-T collector system, over the entire simulation	-

4 Results

The results from the validation of the *tespy* heat pump model developed for this work are presented and discussed in the section 4.1. The results from the simulation of the baseline scenario with only the heat pump are presented and discussed in section 4.2. The results from the simulations of the different configurations of the PV-T SAHP system, the only PV and heat pump simulations, and the simulation of the PV-T SAHP system with the advanced control strategy, are presented and discussed in section 4.3

4.1 Validation

The results of the validation of the *tespy* heat pump model developed for this work are presented and discussed here. The results from the simulations with reduced demands are presented in section 4.1.1. Based on these results, the selection of the most suitable heat pump model for the different system simulations shown in table 3.12, is discussed in section 4.1.2. The results from the simulations of all the heat pump models with full demands are presented in Appendix B.

The control strategy 1 for the heat pump, described in section 3.2.4.3, is used to control the operation of the heat pump to maintain the temperature of the hot water tank, in the simulations with both full demands and the reduced demands. Though the highest temperature needed for the hot water supply is 40°C, the set point for the domestic hot water supply as explained in section 3.1.1, for the validation simulations, the temperature of the bottom layer of the tank is maintained between a lower set point of 40°C ($T_{hp_sp_l}$) and a higher set point of 50°C ($T_{hp_sp_h}$). This is done in order to ensure the hot water tank has sufficient heat to withstand the periods of high demands during the year, and reduce the dependence on the backup heaters.

4.1.1 Simulations with reduced demands

The heat supply from the *hplib* model is insufficient for the full building thermal demands and leads to a skewed comparison of the different heat pump models, with only the *tespy* model being able to maintain the hot water tank at the required level, despite using higher temperature control limits for the hot water tank than required. The heating capacity of the *hplib* model is approximately 38% of the heating capacity of *tespy* model, as shown in Appendix B.2. Therefore, the demands described in figure 3.3 are reduced by a factor of three and used for the simulations of the system with the different heat pump models and their configurations, for a fairer comparison.

4.1.1.1 Building thermal demands

The reduced demand profile is shown in figure 4.1, in terms of the heat supplied, as the demands are always fully met, either by the hot water tank or by the backup heaters. The space heating (SH) demand/supply values, available in kW, are shown directly. The domestic hot water (DHW) demands, available in L, are converted to corresponding power values using the flows from the hot water tank and temperature of the water supply and the incoming cold water for every timestep of the simulation. The thus converted DHW demand/supply values are shown in the figure. The total heat supply, calculated as the sum of the SH and DHW supply values, is also shown

Figure 4.1: Heat Supply/Demand Profile – Reduced Demands

The peak value for the total heat supply, averaged over a whole day, is 8.29 kW and occurs on day 347 of the year, as can be seen in figure 4.1. The peak value for the heat supply in a particular time step, not directly reflected in this figure, is 36.02 kW. The peak values for the SH and DHW supply, averaged over a whole day, are 3.79 kW (day 46 of the year) and 5.57 kW (day 361 of the year) respectively, as can be seen in figure 4.1, whereas the peak values for a particular time step are 10.67 kW and 32.02 kW respectively.

Figure 4.2: Monthly Heat Supply/Demand – Reduced Demands

The figure 4.2 shows the monthly aggregates, in kWh, of the heat supply/demand data shown in figure 4.1. The peak values for the SH and DHW supply, 1234.55 kWh and 2213.7 kWh respectively, are both observed in the month of December 2020, leading to a peak value of 3447.81 kWh for the total heat supply. The lowest values for the SH and DHW supply, 776.76 kWh and 1743.28 kWh respectively, are both observed in the month of September 2020, leading to a lowest value of 2520.03 kWh for the total heat supply.

As explained in section 3.3, all the configurations of the heat pump models are simulated to meet the same reduced building thermal demands, and therefore they have the same heat supply profiles shown in figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1.1.2 Heat pump heat supply

The heat supplied to the hot water tank by the different heat pump models, in terms of the cumulative monthly heat supplied, is compared in the figure 4.3. The heating capacity of the heat pump is dependent primarily on the source air temperature. Since these conditions are the same for both the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* model, the heat supplied is the same in both the cases. Therefore, the comparison of only the *fixed_evap_m* configuration of the *tespy* models with the *hplib* model is shown.

Figure 4.3: Comparison of the cumulative monthly heat supplied by the different heat pump models

The three heat pump models supply very similar amount of heat to the hot water tank throughout the year, with a maximum difference of only 30 kWh observed between the heat supplied by the *tespy_fixed_evap_m* and the *hplib* models in the month of December. The heat supplied is slightly higher than the corresponding monthly demands, shown in figure 4.2, to compensate to the thermal losses from the hot water tank to the surroundings.

The heat supplied to the hot water tank by the different heat pump models, in terms of the heating capacity averaged over a day, is compared in figure 4.4. The comparison of only the *fixed_evap_m* configuration of the *tespy* models with the *hplib* model is shown, due to the similarity of the performance of the configurations as explained earlier.

Figure 4.4: Heat supplied by the different heat pump models – reduced demands

The *tespy* model has the highest heat supply of all the models, with a peak value of 48.15 kW, averaged over a day, and a maximum heat supply of 51 kW for a particular time step. The *tespy_1stage* model has a peak heat supply of 27.12 kW, averaged over a day, and a maximum heat supply of 29.15 kW for a particular time step. The *hplib* model has the lowest heat supply of all the models, with a peak value of 18.78 kW, averaged over a day, and a maximum heat supply of 19.30 kW for a particular time step. It can be seen in figure 4.4, that the *hplib* model supplies heat on all the days of the year, and is no longer non-operational on some days as in the case with full demands.

In the summer months, due to the higher source air temperatures, both the *tespy* and the *tespy_1stage* models can operate at higher heating capacities, which is reflected in the higher heat supply for both the models, as can be seen in the figure 4.4. The *hplib* model, however, has lower heat supply during these days as compared to the other periods of the year. In the *hplib* model, the heating capacity of the heat pump is calculated by multiplying the electrical power of the heat pump with the COP, which are estimated using the parametric fit equations, as explained in section 3.2.1.1. At higher source air temperatures, the COP is estimated to increase, whereas the estimated electrical power decreases. This leads to the overall lower heating capacity. This is not in line with the heat pump performance curves from the manufacturer, shown in figure 3.6, where the electrical power of the heat pump does not reduce at higher source air temperatures.

4.1.1.3 Hot water tank temperature profiles

The temperature profiles of the hot water tank, for the simulations with the *tespy*, *tespy_1stage*, and the *hplib* models, are shown in figures 4.5. The temperatures of all the layers in the tank, the mean temperature of the water inside the tank and the ambient temperature, averaged over a day, are shown in the figure. The heat supply of both the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy/tespy_1stage* models being the same, the temperature profile of the hot water tank also remains the same. Therefore, the profiles of only the *fixed_evap_m* configuration are shown in the figure.

Figure 4.5: Hot water tank temperature profile for the simulations with all heat pump models– reduced demands

The temperature of the bottom layer of the tank ($Temp_layer_0$) is maintained within the range of control of 40⁰C and 50⁰C, by all the heat pump models, as the heat supply of all the models is sufficient to meet the reduced building thermal demands.

4.1.1.4 Coefficient of Performance (COP) of the heat pump

The performance of the heat pump, in terms of its coefficient of performance (COP), estimated by the different heat pump models is compared and analyzed in this section.

The COP of the heat pump plotted against the temperature lift, for the different heat pump models and their configurations, is shown in figure 4.6. Due to the similarity in the performance of the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* and *tespy_1stage* models, they are shown in separate plots.

Figure 4.6: COP of the heat pump vs. Temperature Lift – reduced demands

The scatter plots show all the observed COP values of the heat pump at a particular temperature lift. For the same temperature lift, different source air temperatures and the condenser water outlet temperatures result in a different COP of the heat pump. The average of all these COP values at a particular temperature lift are shown in the plot on the right in the figure 4.6.

The COP of the heat pump is higher at low temperature lift conditions, and reduces with increasing temperature lift, for all the models, as expected. The *tespy* model has a lower COP as compared to the other models, as expected from the manufacturer’s curve shown in figure 3.6. The *hplib* model has a higher COP as compared to both the *tespy* models, with the *tespy_1stage* model being closer to it. At very high temperature lifts, the COPs of the three models are closer with a difference of around 0.1 between the average values. With decreasing temperature lift, the difference in COPs increases, to around 0.7 between the *hplib* and the *tespy* model. It can also be observed, both from the scatter plot and the average COP plot, that the

COP of the *hplib* model has a linear fit, whereas the COPs of the *tespy* models have a non-linear fit with a higher slope at low temperature lift conditions, as expected from the literature, from the curves shown in figure 2.1. The *fixed_evap_m* configuration of *tespy_1stage* model, results in a higher COP in a few cases at temperature lift conditions between 20°C and 40°C, the points straying from the cluster as seen in the plot on the left. This happens in the cases where the bottom layer of the hot water tank is close to the set point, resulting in a part-load operation of the heat pump. However, overall, the COPs of the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* and the *tespy_1stage* models do not deviate much as seen in the average COP plot on the right in the figure 4.6.

In the left side plot of figure 4.7, the average COP curves of all the models are compared against the COP curves available in the manufacturer’s datasheet, for both the 1 stage (*datasheet_1stage*) and 2 stages (*datasheet_2stage*) of compression and for condenser water outlet temperatures of 35°C (*datasheet_Xstage_35*) and 55°C (*datasheet_Xstage_55*). The plot on the right shows the average condenser outlet water temperature observed at the different temperature lift conditions, for all the heat pump models. The *tespy* model is compared against the manufacturer’s curves for two stages of compression configuration, whereas the *hplib* and *tespy_1stage* models are compared against the one stage of compression configuration.

Figure 4.7: COP of the heat pump vs Temperature Lift comparison with manufacturer’s curves – reduced demands

While the manufacturer’s curves are available only for the condenser water outlet temperatures 35°C and 55°C, the condenser water outlet temperature from all the heat pump models ranges between 45°C to 55°C, due to the control range applied on the bottom layer of the hot water tank, which is maintained between 40°C and 50°C as shown in figure 4.10. The lowest temperature lift conditions of around 14°C occur when the condenser water outlet temperatures are the lowest, at around 44°C, and the source air temperature is the highest, at around 30°C. The highest temperature lift conditions of around 57°C occur when the condenser water outlet temperatures are the highest, at around 55°C, and the source air temperature is the lowest, at around -2°C. As the temperature lift increases, the average condenser water outlet temperature also increases steadily, with a reduction only occurring at temperature lifts of around 22°C. This reduction is due to the lower condenser water outlet temperatures in the beginning of the year, when the initial temperature of the tank is 20°C and must be brought within the control range. The source air temperatures during period are around 2°C.

At lower temperature lifts, the heat pump operates at a higher COP for a lower condenser water outlet temperature and as the temperature lift increases, the heat pump operates at a higher COP for a higher condenser water outlet temperature, as observed from the COP curves available in manufacturer’s datasheet. The point of intersection of the 35⁰C and 55⁰C curves is around a temperature lift of 26⁰C and 32⁰C for the one stage and two stages of compression configurations respectively. The COP curves of the *tespy* and the *tespy_1stage* models lie between the manufacturer’s curves for 35⁰C and 55⁰C, as expected, given the condenser water outlet temperature lies in between these two temperatures, with the COP curves coming close to the 55⁰C curve from the datasheet at increasing temperature lift conditions, as the condenser water outlet temperature gets closer to 55⁰C. The *hplib* model, however, overestimates the COP of the heat pump as observed from its COP curve, which lies above the manufacturer’s curves for temperature lifts below 40⁰C, and lies very close to the *datasheet_1stage_55* curve for temperature lifts between 40⁰C and 57⁰C.

The COP of the heat pump plotted against the condenser water outlet temperature, for the different heat pump models and their configurations, is shown in figure 4.8. Due to the similarity in the performance of the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* and *tespy_1stage* models, they are shown in separate plots.

Figure 4.8: COP of the heat pump vs Condenser Water Outlet Temperature – reduced demands

As explained earlier in this section, the condenser water outlet temperature lies between 44⁰C and 55⁰C, with *tespy* model having the lowest COPs and the *hplib* model having the highest COPs. The *hplib* model has some operating points with the condenser water outlet temperature between 40⁰C and 45⁰C, due to the lower heating capacities insufficient to maintain the temperature within the control range during periods of high demands. As explained earlier, the hot water tank has an initial temperature of 20⁰C, and is heated to bring the temperature within the control range, resulting in the lower condenser water outlet temperatures between 25⁰C and 44⁰C seen in the plots. The source air temperature in the initial period is around 2⁰C, resulting in temperature lifts ranging from 23⁰C to 42⁰C. The COP curve of the *hplib* model follows a linear fit, whereas the COP curves of the *tespy* and the *tespy_1stage* models follow a non-linear fit. At the lowest condenser water outlet temperatures, therefore the lowest temperature lifts, the *tespy_1stage* model has higher COPs as compared to the *hplib* model, as expected from the literature, from the curves shown in figure 2.2.

The COP of the heat pump plotted against the source air temperature, for the different heat pump models and their configurations, is shown in figure 4.9. Due to the similarity in the performance of the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* and *tespy_1stage* models, they are shown in separate plots.

Figure 4.9: COP of the heat pump vs Source Air Temperature – reduced demands

The source air temperature ranges from -3°C to 32°C , and with the condenser water outlet temperature limited between 44°C and 55°C , the temperature lift decreases as the source air temperature increases, resulting in an increase in the COP of all the heat pump models. As seen earlier, the *hplib* model has the highest COPs and the *tespy* model the lowest COPs. The higher COPs observed for all the models at the source air temperature of around 2°C is during the initial heating of the hot water tank as explained earlier.

The COP of the heat pump plotted against the temperature lift, and segregated for the different ranges of source air temperature is shown in figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10: COP of the heat pump vs. Temperature Lift vs. Source Air Temperature – reduced demands

The curved fit of the COP curves of the *tespy* and the *tespy_1stage* models and the straight line fit of the COP curves of the *hplib* model are clearer when the curves of segregated for the

different ranges of the source air temperatures. Since the condenser water outlet temperature is maintained within the narrow range of control, the higher temperature lifts occur when the source air temperatures are lower. As the source air temperature increases, the temperature lift reduces for all the heat pump models. Only in the source air temperature range of 0°C to 5°C, the temperature lift drops up to 22°C, due to the initial heating of the tank as explained earlier. In this temperature range, the *hplib* model has a higher COP at higher temperature lifts, but as the temperature lift decreases, the COP of the *tespy_1stage* model is higher, as a result of a higher rate of increase in COP as expected from the literature, from the curves shown in figure 2.2.

4.1.1.5 System performance comparison

The comparison of the performance of the different heat pump models is done using the KPIs shown in table 3.11, and is summarized below in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: System performance comparison of the heat pump models for the validation scenario with reduced demands

System Performance KPIs	Heat Pump Model					Unit
	<i>tespy</i>		<i>tespy_1stage</i>		<i>hplib</i>	
	<i>fixed_evap_m</i>	<i>variable_evap_m</i>	<i>fixed_evap_m</i>	<i>variable_evap_m</i>		
Total Electrical Energy	12795.78	12811.07	11997.90	12001.58	11285.90	KWH
HP Electrical Energy	12795.77	12811.06	11997.74	12001.42	11285.67	KWH
Total Thermal Energy	37993.63	37993.63	38002.37	38002.37	38146.03	KWH
HP Thermal Energy	37993.62	37993.62	38002.21	38002.21	38145.80	KWH
HR SH Energy	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	KWH
HR DHW Energy	0.01	0.01	0.16	0.16	0.23	KWH
HP Startups	1768	1768	1305	1305	1131	-
HR SH Startups	0	0	0	0	0	-
HR DHW Startups	1	1	3	3	3	-
Average SoC	50.87	50.87	50.89	50.89	50.88	°C
Average COP	2.969	2.966	3.167	3.166	3.380	-

As explained earlier, the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* model differ only in terms of the electrical power and in turn the COP of the heat pump, with the electrical power consumption of the *variable_evap_m* configuration being slightly higher than that of the *fixed_evap_m* configuration. For the *tespy* model, a difference of 15.29 kWh or a 0.12% increase is observed, whereas for the *tespy_1stage* model, a difference of 3.68 kWh or a 0.03% increase is observed.

All the heat pump models meet the reduced demands as can be seen from the near zero startups of the backup heaters and the similar average SoC of the hot water tank. The small difference in the thermal energy is due to the difference in the heat loss from the hot water tank to the surroundings over the course of the year. As shown in the previous section, the *tespy* model has the lowest average COP and the *hplib* model the highest COP, resulting in the highest electrical energy consumption by the *tespy* model and the lowest by the *hplib* model. The difference in the heating capacities of the models shown in figure 4.4, is also reflected in the number of startups of the heat pump, with the *tespy* model having the highest startups due to its higher heating capacity, and the *hplib* model having the lowest startups due to its lower heating capacity.

4.1.2 Selection of heat pump model for further system simulations

The overall performance of the *tespy_Istage* and the *hplib* models is comparable, having similar heating capacities, as seen from the system performance KPIs of the simulations with the reduced demands. The *tespy_Istage* heat pump model can be deemed validated. The key differences between the *tespy_Istage* model and the *hplib* model in the estimation of the COP, have been highlighted in section 4.1.1.4. The *hplib* model overestimates the COP of the heat pump and the *tespy/tespy_Istage* model is closer, as compared to the manufacturer's datasheets. Moreover, the *tespy_Istage* model has a better estimation of the COP at low temperature lift conditions, which are more likely when the PV-T system is operated along with the heat pump. Since both the *tespy* and the *tespy_Istage* heat pump models are based on the TESPy library and have been developed following a similar methodology, the *tespy* model can also be deemed validated, given the similar estimation of the COP of the heat pump by both the models as compared to the respective manufacturer's curves, as shown in section 4.1.1.4.

As shown in section 4.1.1.2, the *tespy* model has the highest heating capacity of the three models. Moreover, the *hplib* model has an especially low heating capacity at higher source air temperatures, which are more likely when the PV-T system is operated along with the heat pump. The *tespy* model is better suited, in terms of the heating capacity, to meet the full building thermal demands, as also seen from the Appendix B.1. The *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* model, perform in a similar manner with a maximum difference of 0.13% in the electrical energy consumed, and the COP, of the heat pump, observed in the system simulations with the full demands. The *fixed_evap_m* configuration is chosen to maintain a constant mass flow of air in the PV-T collector system. All the further system simulations are therefore done using the *tespy_fixed_evap_m* heat pump model.

4.2 Baseline scenario simulation

The results of the system simulation without considering the PV-T collector system and with just the external air as the heat source for the heat pump are presented in this section. This simulation is the baseline case that the other simulations with the PV-T collector system are compared against, to assess the relative benefit of heating the source air for the heat pump in the PV-T collector system.

The *tespy_fixed_evap_m* heat pump model is simulated with the full building thermal demands shown in figure 3.3. While the control strategy 1 for the heat pump, is used in the simulations for validation, in this case, the control strategy 2 for the heat pump, described in section 3.2.4.4, is used to control the operation of the heat pump to maintain the temperature of the hot water tank. The control temperatures are reduced, as compared to the validation simulations, as the heating capacity of the *tespy* model is suitable for the demands. A lower temperature limit of 37°C ($T_{hp_sp_l}$) and a higher temperature limit of 43°C ($T_{hp_sp_h}$) are used, to maintain the hot water tank at a temperature slightly higher than the 40°C required for the domestic hot water supply. Though the required SH supply water temperature is lower at 35°C, the control limits are based only on the DHW supply temperature, due to the much higher instantaneous peak demands for the DHW.

4.2.1 Heat pump heat supply

The heat supplied by the heat pump to the hot water tank is shown in the plot on the left in figure 4.11. The ambient temperature, which is also the source air temperature for the heat pump is shown in the plot on the right.

Figure 4.11: Heat Supplied by the heat pump – baseline scenario

The heating capacity of the heat pump is dependent only on the source air temperature and the heat supplied by the heat pump follows a curve very similar to that of the ambient temperature, as can be seen in the figure.

The peak value of the heat supplied by the heat pump, averaged over a day, is 48.47 kW, which occurs on day 221 of the year, as can be seen in the figure. The source air temperature on this day is among the highest in the year, allowing the heat pump to operate at higher heating capacities. The peak value of the heat supplied at a particular timestep, not directly seen in the figure, is 51 kW.

The lowest amount of heat supplied by the heat pump, averaged over a day, is 28.19 kW, which occurs on day 2 of the year, as can be seen in the figure. The source air temperature on this day is among the lowest in the year, resulting in lower heating capacity of the heat pump. The lowest value of heat supplied at a particular timestep, not directly seen in the figure, is 27.1 kW.

4.2.2 Hot water tank temperature profile

The temperature profile of the hot water tank is shown in figures 4.12. The temperatures of all the layers in the tank and the mean temperature of the water inside the tank, averaged over a day, are shown in the figure.

Figure 4.12: Hot Water Tank Temperature Profile – baseline scenario

The temperature inside the hot water tank is maintained as per the control strategy explained in section 3.2.4.4 and shown in figure 3.14. The temperature of top layer (*Temp_layer_5*) is maintained below the higher limit of 43⁰C, with a 3⁰C buffer to the desired supply temperature of 40⁰C, to withstand the periods of high demands. The temperature reaches a maximum value of 42.3⁰C, averaged over a day, on day 223 of the year, as can be seen in the figure, and a maximum value of 42.5⁰C, for a particular timestep, not directly seen in the figure. It never breaches the higher limit of 43⁰C at any point during the year.

The temperature of the bottom layer (*Temp_layer_0*) is controlled to be maintained at 37⁰C, which would maintain the top layer above the desired supply temperature of 40⁰C, due to the stratification inside the tank. The temperature reaches a maximum value of 37.44⁰C, averaged over a day, as seen in the figure and a maximum value of 38.58⁰C, at a particular timestep, not directly seen in figure. The overshoot of the temperature beyond the 37⁰C at a timestep happens due to the delay of one timestep in communication between the hot water tank and the heat pump in the co-simulation. When there is no demand and the heat pump operates at a higher heating capacity, the overshoot is as high as 1.58⁰C.

Throughout the year, the temperature of the bottom layer of the tank is brought down from the limit by the incoming cold water from the domestic hot water supply circuit. This can be seen clearly in the figure with the temperature of the bottom layer oscillating between 34⁰C and 37⁰C, while the temperatures of all the other layers are closer and oscillate between 38⁰C and 42.5⁰C, with an average difference of 3.42⁰C between the temperatures of the bottom layer and the first layer.

During periods of high demands and low ambient temperature, and therefore lower heating capacities of the heat pump, the temperature of the bottom layer drops further away from the limit, with a minimum value of 34.51⁰C, averaged over a day, on day 360 of the year, as can be seen in the figure. For a particular timestep, it drops to as low as 19.28⁰C, which is not seen in the figure. Cumulatively, the temperature remains below 35⁰C for about 715 hours of the year, of which only 71 hours are in the summer period (days 150 to 250) when the higher

ambient temperatures allow the heat pump to operate at higher heating capacities, and the remaining 644 hours are in the remaining part of the year.

The temperature of the top layer is partly shielded from this variance due to the stratification inside the tank. While this temperature, averaged over a day, never drops below the DHW supply temperature of 40⁰C, for a particular timestep, it drops to as low as 30.9⁰C. Cumulatively, the temperature remains below 40⁰C for about 302 hours of the year, of which only 5 hours are in the summer period (days 150 to 250), and the remaining 297 hours are in the remaining part of the year.

4.2.3 System performance comparison

The performance of the system, measured by the KPIs identified in table 3.11, is summarized in table 4.2. The additional KPIs identified in table 3.12 are not applicable as the system simulations are performed only with the heat pump and without the PV-T collector system. The system performance results of the *tespy_fixed_evap_m* model with full demands, shown in table B.1, are also presented here for comparison.

Table 4.2: System performance for the baseline scenario

System Performance KPIs	Heat Pump Model		Unit
	<i>tespy_fixed_evap_m</i>		
	<i>Validation</i>	<i>Baseline</i>	
Total Electrical Energy	36142.91	31476.52	KWH
HP Electrical Energy	36137.98	30779.48	KWH
Total Thermal Energy	110661.23	110221.04	KWH
HP Thermal Energy	110656.30	109524.01	KWH
HR SH Energy	4.06	313.47	KWH
HR DHW Energy	0.87	383.56	KWH
HP Startups	2464	38182	-
HR SH Startups	3	116	-
HR DHW Startups	3	169	-
Average SoC	50.62	40.47	°C
Average COP	3.062	3.558	-

As a result of the new control strategy used, with lower control limit temperatures, the mean temperature inside the hot water tank (*average SoC*), drops as expected. This leads to reduced condenser water temperatures for the heat pump, and consequently lower temperature lifts, resulting in better electrical performance, reflected in the 14.8% reduction in the electrical energy consumed by the heat pump and an increase of 16.2% in the COP of the heat pump.

The reduced temperatures, increase the reliance of the system on the backup heaters for both the space heating and the domestic hot water demands, reflected in the number of startups and the energy consumption of the backup heaters. The reduction in the thermal energy delivered by the heat pump is however limited to only 1%. The overall thermal energy delivered by the system is also slightly lower, 0.3%, due to the reduced heat loss from the hot water tank to the surroundings with lower temperatures inside the tank.

The significantly higher number of startups in the baseline scenario can be attributed to two factors. First, the lower control band for the temperatures, which is 6⁰C in the baseline scenario

as compared to the 10⁰C in the validation scenario. Second, shifting the control basis to both the top and bottom layers of the hot water tank in the baseline scenario, instead of only the bottom layer as done in validation scenario.

4.3 PV-T SAHP system simulations

The results of the simulations of the SAHP system, mentioned in table 3.12, are presented in this section. The *tespy_fixed_evap_m* heat pump model and the same temperature control limits as used in the baseline case have been used for all the simulations. The results of the simulations of the system for the different configurations of the PV-T system are presented in section 4.3.1. The results of the simulations of the system with only the PV modules and the heat pump are presented in section 4.3.2. The results of the system simulations with the advanced control strategy are presented in section 4.3.3.

4.3.1 Simulations of different configurations of PV-T system

As explained in section 3.4, different configurations of the PV-T collector system, with 2,4,6,8,10 and 12 panels connected in series, are simulated along with the heat pump. In each case, the PV-T collector system has 133 strings connected in parallel in order to maintain the required mass flowrate of air in the evaporator of the heat pump. At the times when the heat pump is not in operation, the thermal component of the PV-T collector system is also considered to not be in operation, with only the PV component potentially generating electrical energy.

4.3.1.1 Heat pump heat supply

The heat supplied by the heat pump to the hot water tank, for the different configurations of the PV-T system, are compared with the baseline case of the system with only the heat pump, in figure 4.13. The different configurations are labelled according to the number PV-T collector panels connected in series and the number of such strings in parallel. For ex., the PV-T collector system configuration with 2 panels in series and 133 strings in parallel is labelled '2*133'.

Figure 4.13: Comparison of heat supplied by the heat pump to the hot water tank for the different configurations of PV-T system

As can be seen in the figure 4.13, the heat supplied in the baseline case with only the heat pump is lower during almost the entire year than when the PV-T system is operated along with the heat pump. During the winter period with lower radiation (days 1 to 50, and days 310 to 366), the heat supplied in the baseline case, and by the different configurations of the PV-T system, is similar, due to the low increase in temperature of the source air in the PV-T system. During periods of higher radiation in the rest of the year, the heat supplied increases with the increasing number of PV-T panels in series, due to the higher source air temperatures generated by the PV-T system. However, during the summer period (days 150 to 250), the difference in the heat supplied in the various cases is lower, due to the already high ambient temperature, and lower potential for increase of the source air temperature within the PV-T system.

The peak values for the heat supplied in the different cases, averaged over a day, and the day of the year in which they occur; the peak values for a particular timestep; and the maximum increase in the heat supplied in the various cases as compared to the baseline case, have been summarized in table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Comparison of heat supplied for the different configurations of PV-T system

System Configuration	Peak Value, Daily Average		Instantaneous Peak value (kW)	Maximum Increase	
	Heat Supplied (kW)	Day of year		Heat Supplied (kW)	% change from baseline
Baseline	48.47	221	51	30.06	-
2*133	50.61	221	54	35.33	17.53
4*133	51.31	225	54	38.08	26.68
6*133	51.61	225	54	39.43	31.17
8*133	51.73	225	54	40.34	34.20
10*133	51.54	229	54	40.78	35.66
12*133	51.37	226	54	41.02	36.46

The peak values for the heat supplied, averaged over a day, for the different configurations are observed in the summer. However, the difference in the values from the baseline is not the highest due to the high heat supplied in the baseline case itself as a result of the high ambient temperatures during the summer.

The maximum increase in the heat supplied for the different configurations, as compared to the baseline case, is observed on day 82 of the year, with a high average incident radiation of 325.92 W/m² and an average ambient temperature of 2.84°C. While there are other days in the summer with higher incident radiation, the higher ambient temperature leads to a lower relative increase when the PV-T system is used. It can be observed that with the increasing number of panels in series, the relative change in the increase of the heat supplied reduces.

4.3.1.2 Hot water tank temperatures

The comparison of the mean temperature of the hot water tank for the simulations of the different configurations of the PV-T system with that of the baseline case with only the heat pump is shown in figure 4.14. The different configurations are labelled in a manner similar to that of the heat pump heat supply shown in figure 4.13.

Figure 4.14: Comparison of the mean hot water tank temperature for the different configurations of PV-T system

As can be seen from the figure 4.14, between the days 70 to 270 of the year, the mean temperatures of hot water tank, averaged over a day, of the cases with higher PV-T collector panels in series, are lower than that of the baseline case. This is a result of the way the heat pump model has been developed to turn off in the conditions where the source air temperature is close to the condenser water inlet temperature. During periods of high radiation and/or high ambient temperature, the outlet temperatures from the PV-T system, especially that of the configurations with higher panels in series, are closer to the control range of the water inside the tank, i.e., the condenser water inlet temperature. When these conditions coincide with periods of high demands, the temperature of the water inside the tank drops below the source air temperature, and the heat pump turns off. In the baseline case, and in the case with only 2 PV-T collector panels in series, this condition does not arise as frequently as in the other cases. During the rest of the year, the radiation and the ambient air temperature are low enough to prevent such a condition from arising.

It should however be noted that the lowest mean temperature of the water in the tank observed is around 36.5°C , and in most other cases, the temperature is within the control limits of 37°C and 43°C . Therefore, this does not lead to a significant increase in the dependence on the back up heaters, which will also be shown later in the section 4.3.1.6.

4.3.1.3 Heat Pump source air and PV-T outlet temperatures

The ambient air is heated in the PV-T collector system before being used as the source air in the heat pump. As explained in 3.2.3.4, in the cases when the temperature at the outlet of the PV-T system is greater than the temperature limit for the operation of the heat pump, the outlet air is mixed with ambient air to reduce the temperature to the temperature limit. The heat pump source air temperature, labelled '*HP_evap_T*', and the outlet temperature from the PV-T collector system before mixing with the ambient air, labelled '*PVT_T_out*', for the different configurations, are shown as a duration curve in the figure 4.15. The different configurations of the PV-T collector system are labelled in a manner similar to that of the figure 4.13.

Figure 4.15: Duration curve of the heat pump source air and PV-T system outlet temperatures for the different configurations of PV-T system

The heat pump must operate for the longest time in the baseline case, and the operation time decreases with increasing number of PV-T collector panels connected in series, due to the higher heat pump heating capacities as explained in section 4.3.1.1. As expected, the higher the number of PV-T collector panels connected in series, the higher the maximum PV-T outlet temperature observed. Moreover, the duration for which the source air temperature to the heat pump is at the maximum limit of 35⁰C increases, with an increase in the number of panels in series. The maximum temperatures and durations are summarized in table 4.4. It can be observed that with the increasing number of panels in series, the relative increase in the duration at maximum source air temperature, which leads to better heat pump performance, and the relative decrease in the duration of heat pump operation, both reduce.

Table 4.4: Comparison of the heat pump operation, source air temperature and PV-T outlet temperature for the different configurations of PV-T system

System Configuration	Heat Pump Operation		Maximum PV-T Outlet Temperature (deg. C)	HP Source Air Temperature	
	Duration (minutes)	% change from baseline		Maximum Value (deg. C)	Duration at Maximum Value (minutes)
Baseline	177,491	-		31.61	2
2*133	170,855	-3.74	44.02	35	1,280
4*133	167,214	-5.79	54.68	35	5,947
6*133	164,997	-7.04	63.61	35	9,489
8*133	163,568	-7.84	71.00	35	11,779
10*133	162,578	-8.40	77.09	35	13,109
12*133	161,862	-8.81	82.18	35	13,966

4.3.1.4 Coefficient of Performance (COP) of the heat pump

The comparison of the coefficient of performance (COP) of the heat pump, of the different cases simulated, is shown as a duration curve in the figure 4.16. The different cases are labelled as done in the figure 4.13.

Figure 4.16: Duration curve of the COP of the heat pump for the different configurations of PV-T system

The COP of the heat pump at the limit source air temperature of 35°C and for a condenser water outlet temperature of 35°C is slightly higher than 6.5, as seen in the manufacturer's curve shown in figure 3.6. However, the maximum COP that can be seen in the figure 4.16 is close to 13. These higher COPs occur at the times when the heat pump operates at a part load, when the temperature of the water inside the tank is very close to the control limits, and the resultant heat demand is lower than the heating capacity of the heat pump. For the different cases simulated, the maximum COP observed, and the duration for which the part load operation occurs, measured as the times with COP greater than 6.5, are summarized in table 4.5. The part load operation occurs for a very small duration over the course of the year.

As expected from the trend in the maximum source air temperature of 35°C for the different configurations, shown in figure 4.15, the duration for which the heat pump operates at a high COP as a result of these high source air temperatures increases with increasing number of panels in series, as seen in the flat lines above the COP of 5.75 in the figure 4.16. The duration for which the heat pump operates at these high COPs for the different configurations is also summarized in table 4.5. With increasing number of panels in series, the relative increase in the duration of operation at high COP, reduces, as similarly observed from the duration at maximum source air temperature in table 4.4.

Table 4.5: Comparison of maximum COP and durations for the different configurations of PV-T system

System Configuration	Maximum COP	Duration of part load operation COP>6.5 (minutes)	Duration of high COP COP>5.75 (minutes)
Baseline	8.32	2	5
2*133	11.65	28	1,411
4*133	12.43	43	6,211
6*133	12.72	66	9,675
8*133	13.01	69	12,017
10*133	12.43	69	13,232
12*133	13.01	64	14,092

4.3.1.5 PV-T System and heat pump thermal energy analysis

The thermal energy extracted from the air in the evaporator of heat pump is either supplied by the PV-T collector system or is available from the ambient air. The thermal energy gained by the air in the PV-T collector system is lost when the outlet temperature is greater than the limit temperature of the heat pump, by mixing it with ambient air, or when the energy gained is greater than the requirement in the heat pump. In the cases when the thermal energy gained in the PV-T collector system is insufficient or the system is off, the thermal energy available in the ambient air is used by the heat pump.

In the figure 4.17, the monthly aggregates of the thermal energy gained by the air in the PV-T system that is used in the heat pump, labelled ' Q_{PVT_used} ', the corresponding energy lost, labelled ' Q_{PVT_lost} ', and the thermal energy from the ambient air that is used, labelled ' Q_{amb} ', are shown for the different configurations of the PV-T collector system.

Figure 4.17: Comparison of the thermal energy from the PV-T system and ambient air for the different configurations of the PV-T system

The total thermal energy used in the evaporator of the heat pump, the sum of ' Q_{PVT_used} ' and ' Q_{amb} ,' is similar for all the different configurations. This is expected as the total thermal energy delivered by the heat pump is similar in all the cases as they have the same building thermal demands. The small increasing trend with the increasing number of panels in series, with a maximum difference of 259 kWh between the configurations with 2 and 12 panels in series observed in the month of March, is due to the differences in the electrical performance, i.e., the COP, of the heat pumps in the different configurations.

During the summer months, with high radiation and higher ambient temperature, the ' Q_{PVT_used} ' is higher as compared to that in the winter periods, for all the configurations of the PV-T system. Of the total thermal energy used in the evaporator of the heat pump, the ' Q_{PVT_used} ' comprises a share of 65% and 37%, for the 12 and 2 panels in series configurations respectively, in the month of April. Conversely, the share reduces to 17% and 5% for the 12 and 2 panels in series configurations respectively, in the month of January.

Similarly, ' Q_{PVT_lost} ' is higher in the summer months and lower in the winter months for all the configurations of the PV-T system, with the highest and lowest values of 3,395 kWh and 150 kWh in the months of April and January respectively for the configuration with 12 panels in series, and the highest value of 140 kWh in August and no energy being lost in December for the configuration with 2 panels in series.

The ' Q_{PVT_used} ' increases with an increasing number of panels in series, throughout the year, with a maximum difference of 2,621 kWh between the configurations with 2 and 12 panels in series observed in the month of May. Consequently, the ' Q_{amb} ' decreases as the number of panels in series increase with a maximum difference of 2,373 kWh between the configurations with 2 and 12 panels in series observed in the month of May. The ' Q_{PVT_lost} ' also increases with an increasing number of panels in series, throughout the year, with a maximum difference of 3,392 kWh between the configurations with 2 and 12 panels in series observed in the month of April.

4.3.1.6 System performance comparison

The performance of the system for the different configurations, measured by the KPIs identified in table 3.11 and table 3.12, is summarized in table 4.6.

The total thermal energy for all the cases is almost the same, with the heat pump supplying most of the thermal energy. The thermal energy supplied by the backup heaters is significantly lower. As explained in section 4.3.1.2, the reliance on backup heaters increases with increasing number of panels in series, which can be seen from the increasing backup heater energies and the startups, and the decreasing average SoC. However, the share of the backup heater thermal energy in the total thermal energy is a maximum of 0.65% for the '12*133' configuration of the PV-T system. The number of startups of the heat pump are significantly higher than that of the backup heaters, and increase with increasing number of panels in series. This is due to the higher heating capacities of the heat pump in configurations with higher panels in series, as explained in section 4.3.1.1.

Table 4.6: System performance comparison of the different configurations of PV-T collector System

System Performance KPIs	Heat Pump Model							Unit
	<i>tespy_fixed_evap_m</i>							
	Baseline	PV-T System Configuration						
	2*133	4*133	6*133	8*133	10*133	12*133		
Total Electrical Energy	31476.52	30312.00	29534.94	29031.57	28712.77	28488.10	28358.63	KWH
HP Electrical Energy	30779.48	29688.75	28883.05	28378.92	28039.34	27815.92	27638.69	KWH
Total Thermal Energy	110221.04	110222.91	110223.50	110222.61	110221.61	110220.59	110218.41	KWH
HP Thermal Energy	109524.01	109599.66	109571.62	109569.96	109548.18	109548.41	109498.47	KWH
HR SH Energy	313.47	284.83	310.17	304.51	312.66	295.55	315.73	KWH
HR DHW Energy	383.56	338.42	341.71	348.14	360.77	376.63	404.21	KWH
HP Startups	38182	38441	38706	39380	39964	40643	41367	-
HR SH Startups	116	102	104	100	103	99	102	-
HR DHW Startups	169	153	164	184	203	229	250	-
Average SoC	40.47	40.53	40.52	40.50	40.47	40.44	40.40	°C
Average COP	3.56	3.69	3.79	3.86	3.91	3.94	3.96	-
PV-T Total Thermal Energy	-	15432.94	26301.77	34849.26	41726.89	47395.89	51968.28	KWH
PV-T Thermal Energy Used	-	15224.87	23522.68	27886.26	30562.60	32371.26	33569.93	KWH
PV-T Excess Thermal Energy	-	208.08	2779.08	6963.00	11164.29	15024.62	18398.35	KWH
Ambient Thermal Energy Used	-	64686.05	57165.89	53304.78	50946.24	49361.23	48289.85	KWH
PV-T Total Electrical Energy	-	17902.47	35548.81	53042.38	70415.59	87690.86	104885.85	KWH
PV-T Electrical Energy Used	-	6033.68	8684.37	9989.67	10870.39	11516.53	12045.5	KWH
PV-T Excess Electrical Energy	-	11868.78	26864.44	43052.71	59545.20	76174.33	92840.35	KWH
Grid Electrical Energy Used	-	24278.32	20850.56	19041.9	17842.38	16971.57	16313.13	KWH
PV-T Thermal Efficiency	-	0.334	0.305	0.280	0.257	0.237	0.219	-
PV-T Electrical Efficiency	-	0.1291	0.1282	0.1275	0.1269	0.1265	0.1261	-

The total electrical energy consumed by the system decreases with increasing number of panels in series, due to the improved performance of the heat pump as seen in the increasing average COP. As explained in 4.3.1.4, the higher source temperatures available for the heat pump in the configurations with higher panels in series, lead to increases in COP. The change in the electric energy and the COP for the different configurations, is shown in figure 4.18, with the labels on the plot lines representing the percentage change from the baseline case. The rate of change of both the electrical energy consumed and the COP, reduces with increasing number of panels in series, as seen in the flattening of the curves.

Figure 4.18: Comparison of system electrical performance for the different configurations of PV-T system

The total thermal energy of the PV-T system, the thermal energy of the PV-T system used in the heat pump, and the excess thermal energy of the PV-T system, increase with increasing number of panels in series, as expected. Consequently, the thermal energy from the ambient

air used in the heat pump decreases with increasing number of panels in series. For the different configurations, the share of the excess thermal energy in the total thermal energy of the PV-T system, and the share of thermal energy from the ambient in the total thermal energy used by the heat pump, are shown in figure 4.19.

Figure 4.19: Comparison of the PV-T system and ambient thermal energy for the different configurations of PV-T system

With increasing number of panels in series, the dependence on ambient thermal energy decreases as the thermal energy of the PV-T system increases, from 80.95% for the 2 panels in series configuration to 58.99% for the 12 panels in series configuration. However, an increasing share of the thermal energy from the PV-T system is in excess to the need, with only 1.35% of excess thermal energy from the PV-T system for the 2 panels in series configuration, and 35.4% of excess for the 12 panels in series configuration. From the figures, it can be seen that the decrease in the dependence on ambient thermal energy is lower than the increase in the excess thermal energy from the PV-T system, as the number of panels in series increase, i.e., the relative benefit of adding more panels in series reduces as the number of panels in series increase, with more excess thermal energy than that used in the heat pump.

The total electrical energy of the PV-T system, the electrical energy of the PV-T system used in the heat pump or the heaters, and the excess electrical energy of the PV-T system, increase with increasing number of panels in series, as expected. Consequently, the electrical energy needed from the grid decreases with increasing number of panels in series. For the different configurations, the share of the excess electrical energy in the total electrical energy of the PV-T system, and the share of electrical energy from the grid in the total electrical energy used by the heat pump and the backup heaters, are shown in figure 4.20.

With increasing number of panels in series, the dependence on electrical energy from the grid decreases as the electrical energy from the PV-T system increases, from 80.09% for the 2 panels in series configuration to 57.52% for the 12 panels in series configuration. However, an increasing share of the electrical energy from the PV-T system is in excess to the need, with 66.3% of excess electrical energy from the PV-T system for the 2 panels in series configuration, and 88.52% of excess for the 12 panels in series configuration. As observed in figure 4.18, the rate of change of the grid electrical energy and the excess electrical energy of the PV-T system, reduces with increasing number of panels in series, as seen in the flattening of the curves in figure 4.20.

Figure 4.20: Comparison of the PV-T system and grid electrical energy for the different configurations of PV-T system

When compared to the thermal energy of the PV-T system, a greater share of electrical energy of the system is in excess to the need, with the 2 panels in series configuration having only 1.35% excess thermal energy as compared to 66.3% excess electrical energy. This can be explained by the fact that the thermal component of the PV-T system is operated only when the heat pump is on, while the electrical energy is generated throughout the year irrespective of the operation of the heat pump.

The thermal and the electrical efficiency of the PV-T system decreases with increasing number of panels in series, due to the higher PV-T system outlet air temperatures for higher number of panels in series, as explained in section 4.3.1.3. The change in the efficiencies for the different configurations, is shown in figure 4.21, with the labels on the plot lines representing the percentage change from the 2 panels in series configuration.

Figure 4.21: Comparison of the PV-T system thermal and electrical efficiency for the different configurations of PV-T system

Most suitable PV-T system configuration for the building thermal demands

Though the electrical performance of the heat pump increases, with an increase in the number of panels in series, the rate of increase/decrease in the COP/total electrical energy consumed reduces, as explained earlier. As can be seen from the figure 4.18, the COP increases by 6.61% with 4 panels in series and by increasing the number of panels in series to 12, the COP is improved further only by an additional 4.73%. The total electrical energy consumed that decreases by 6.17% with 4 panels in series, reduces only by an additional 3.74% by increasing the number of panels in series to 12. Similarly, the grid electrical energy used drops to 70.6% for the system with 4 panels in series, and reduces by only an additional 13.08% by increasing the number of panels in series to 12, as seen in the figure 4.20. The share of excess thermal energy of the PV-T system, which is 10.75% for the system with 4 panels in series, increases by a factor of more than 3 to 35.4% by increasing the number of panels in series to 12, as seen in figure 4.19.

Considering these trends in the performance of the systems, the PV-T system configuration with 4 panels in series is identified as the most suitable one for the building thermal demands. This configuration of the PV-T system will be used for the simulations with the advanced control strategy explained in section 3.4.

4.3.2 Simulations of only the PV and the heat pump system

The results of the simulations of the system with the different configurations of the PV system and the heat pump are summarized in table 4.7. Only selected KPIs that characterize the electrical performance of the PV system are shown, as the other KPIs will be the same as that in the baseline case. The results from the PV-T system are also presented for a comparison of the PV system against the PV-T system.

Table 4.7: Comparison of the electrical performance of the different configurations of PV/PV-T System

System Performance KPIs	Heat Pump Model												Unit
	<i>tespy_fixed_evap_m</i>												
	System Configuration												
	2*133		4*133		6*133		8*133		10*133		12*133		
PV	PV-T	PV	PV-T	PV	PV-T	PV	PV-T	PV	PV-T	PV	PV-T		
Total Electrical Energy	17581.21	17902.47	35162.48	35548.81	52743.72	53042.38	70324.96	70415.59	87906.21	87690.86	105487.4	104885.8	KWH
Electrical Energy Used	6629.871	6033.68	10367.27	8684.37	12276.99	9989.67	13543.48	10870.39	14449.41	11516.53	15142.88	12045.5	KWH
Excess Electrical Energy	10951.37	11868.78	24795.21	26864.44	40466.74	43052.71	56781.49	59545.2	73456.8	76174.33	90344.57	92840.35	KWH
Grid Electrical Energy Used	24846.64	24278.32	21109.24	20850.56	19199.53	19041.9	17933.04	17842.38	17027.11	16971.57	16333.64	16313.13	KWH

The performance of the PV system has similar trends to that of the PV-T system for increasing number of panels in series as expected. The total electrical energy generated by the PV system is lower than the energy generated by the corresponding PV-T system, for the configurations up to 8 panels in series. In these cases, the heat extracted by the collector reduces the cell temperature, thereby increasing the electrical efficiency/electricity generation of the PV-T system. However, for the configurations with 10 and 12 panels in series, the higher temperatures of the fluid in the collectors worsen the efficiency of the PV cell, resulting in a reduction in the electrical energy generated. For these cases, the PV system generates more electrical energy than the PV-T system.

The electrical energy generated by the PV system that is used by the heat pump and back up heaters is greater than the corresponding energy from the PV-T system. This can be attributed to the lower operation duration of the PV-T system as a result of the higher heating capacities of the heat pump, as explained in section 4.3.1.3. This is also reflected in the increasing

difference between the electrical energy from the PV and corresponding PV-T system that is used by the heat pump, as the number of panels in series increase, as shown in the figure 4.22. Consequently, there is lesser excess electrical energy in the cases with the PV system, as compared to that of the cases with corresponding PV-T systems.

Figure 4.22: Comparison of the electrical energy used from the PV/PV-T system and the grid for the different configurations of PV/PV-T system

The grid energy used by the heat pump and the backup heaters in the cases of PV system is higher than the corresponding energy from the PV-T system, for the configurations up to 8 panels in series. This is due to the higher electrical energy consumption of the system in the baseline case, and therefore all the PV cases, as compared to that of the PV-T system cases, as shown in table 4.6. However, in the cases with 10 and 12 panels in series, the higher electrical energy of the PV system that is used, reduces the grid electrical energy used to lower than the corresponding energy in the cases with the PV-T system, as shown in figure 4.22.

4.3.3 Simulation with the advanced control strategy

The results from the simulations of the system with the advanced control strategy, as explained in section 3.4, are presented in this section. The configuration of the PV-T collector with 4 panels in series, which has been identified as the most suitable one for the building thermal demands, has been used for these simulations. The results from these simulations are compared with the results from the simulations with the same configuration of the PV-T system, with 4 panels in series, but with the control strategy 2, that have been presented in section 4.3.1.

4.3.3.1 Heat pump heat supply

The heat supplied by the heat pump to the hot water tank, is shown in figure 4.23, with the heat supply in the case simulated with control strategy 2 labelled as ‘*HP Heat Supply – 4*133*’, and that from the case with the advanced control strategy labelled as ‘*HP Heat Supply – 4*133 – advanced control strategy*’.

Figure 4.23: Comparison of the heat supplied by the heat pump with different control strategies

As can be seen from the figure, the heat supplied by the heat pump in the case with the advance control strategy, is slightly higher, with a maximum difference of 2.75 kW, observed on day 130 of the year. This is due to the fact that with the advanced control strategy, the duration of operation of the heat pump is increased during the times when the PV-T system operates, by increasing the control limits of operation. As a result, the heat pump operates for a longer duration at higher source air temperatures which allow for a higher heating capacity of the heat pump.

4.3.3.2 Hot water tank temperature profiles

The temperature profiles of the hot water tank, for the simulations with the advanced control strategy and the control strategy 2 are shown in the figure 4.24, on the right- and left-hand side respectively. The temperatures of all the layers in the tank, the mean temperature of the water inside the tank and the ambient temperature, averaged over a day, are shown in the figure.

Figure 4.24: Hot water tank temperature profiles for the simulations with different control strategies

The temperatures of different layers of the hot water tank, remain between the control limits of 37°C and 43°C for most days of the year, in the case with the control strategy 2, as expected. However, the temperatures are higher in the case with the advanced control strategy as intended, with the limits being increased based on the temperature gain of air inside the PV-T system. During the summer months, when the temperature gain is higher in the PV-T system, the temperatures in the tank are also higher, as compared to the other months, as can be seen from the trend in the figure. The maximum increase in the control limits is restricted to 7°C, therefore restricting the increase in the hot water tank temperatures to a maximum of 50°C.

The maximum temperatures of the top and the bottom layers, and the maximum mean temperature of the hot water tank in both the cases are summarized in table 4.8.

Table 4.8: Maximum hot water tank temperatures for the simulations with different control strategies

Maximum Hot Water Tank Temperatures	Control Strategy-2	Advanced control strategy	Unit
Top layer	42.32	48.69	deg.C
Bottom layer	37.44	40.91	deg.C
Mean	41.06	45.52	deg.C

4.3.3.3 Weekly performance of the system

In order to study the effect of the advanced control strategy, the performance of the system is observed over a shorter time frame of one week. Four weeks within the year are chosen for this analysis, based on the differences in the inputs to the simulations, i.e., the ambient temperature (T_{amb}), the incident radiation (E), and the building thermal demands ($Demand$), as shown in figure 4.25.

Figure 4.25: Periods chosen for the weekly analysis of the system performance

The four weeks chosen for this analysis and the differences in the inputs during these periods are summarized in table 4.9.

Table 4.9: Periods chosen for the weekly analysis of the system performance

Weeks chosen for the analysis	Days of the year	Inputs to the simulation
07-04 to 13-04	97 to 103	Avg. demand, Avg. T_amb, High E
08-08 to 14-08	221 to 227	Avg. demand, High T_amb, High E
04-09 to 10-09	248 to 254	Low demand, Avg. T_amb, Avg. E
01-12 to 07-12	336 to 342	High demand, Low T_amb, Low E

In the figure 4.26, the results of the weekly analysis for the different periods chosen are shown. The results from the case with the control strategy 2 are shown on the left and the results from the case with the advanced control strategy are shown on the right.

In the figure, the temperature of the air at the inlet and the outlet of the PV-T system, labelled ‘Air – PV-T inlet’ and ‘Air - PV-T outlet’ respectively, the source air temperature for the heat pump, labelled ‘Air – HP inlet’, temperatures of the top and the bottom layers of the hot water tank, labelled ‘HWT – Top layer’ and ‘HWT – Bottom layer’ respectively, and the heat supplied by the heat pump during day time and night time, labelled ‘HP Heat Supply – Day’ and ‘HP Heat Supply – Night’ respectively, are shown.

In each of the plots on the right-hand side, the increase in the hot water tank temperatures, as compared to the corresponding plot on the left, can be seen, during the times when the PV-T system is operational, with the temperatures for the ‘HWT – Top layer’ reaching around 50°C in the plots on the right, and being limited to less than 43°C in the plots on the left.

In the week from April, the high radiation leads to a highest ‘Air – PV-T outlet’ temperature of around 45°C, with the ‘Air – HP inlet’ being restricted to the limit of 35°C. However, in the week from August, due to the already high ambient temperatures, the high radiation leads to a highest ‘Air – PV-T outlet’ temperature of around 55°C. In the week from September, the lower radiation when compared to the weeks from April and August, leads to a highest ‘Air – PV-T outlet’ temperature of only around 35°C. In the week from December, with the lowest radiation and low ambient temperatures, the highest ‘Air – PV-T outlet’ temperature of only around 18°C is observed.

Because of the lower ‘Air – PV-T outlet’ temperatures in the week from December, the heat supplied by the heat pump is also lower during this week, with most operational points between 30-35 kW, whereas during the other weeks, most of the operational points above 40 kW. Due to the high demands during this week, the operational points of the heat pump are also higher as compared to the other weeks. The total duration of operation of the heat pump and the duration of operation during daytime and nighttime, for both the control strategies used, are summarized in table 4.10.

Figure 4.26: Weekly performance analysis of the PV-T SAHP system

Table 4.10: Comparison of the duration of heat pump operation for the different control strategies

Weeks chosen for the analysis	Duration of heat pump operation (minutes)					
	Control Strategy -2			Advanced Control Strategy		
	Total	Day	Night	Total	Day	Night
07-04 to 13-04	3096	2481	615	3052	2549	503
08-08 to 14-08	2494	2132	362	2498	2172	326
04-09 to 10-09	1929	1468	461	1926	1549	377
01-12 to 07-12	4437	1749	2688	4425	1857	2568

The total duration of the heat pump operation, influenced by the level of demand, is highest during the high demand week from December, and lowest during the low demand period of September. In each of the weeks, with the advanced control strategy, the duration of operation during the daytime increases, and the duration of operation during nighttime decreases, as intended.

4.3.3.4 System performance comparison

The performance of the system, measured by the KPIs identified in table 3.11 and table 3.12, and by the duration of operation of the heat pump, for the control strategies implemented, is summarized in table 4.11.

Table 4.11: Comparison of the system performance for the different control strategies

System Performance KPIs	Control Strategy Used		Unit
	Control Strategy -2	Advanced Control Strategy	
Total Electrical Energy	29534.94	30035.28	KWH
HP Electrical Energy	28883.05	29497.40	KWH
Total Thermal Energy	110223.50	110326.79	KWH
HP Thermal Energy	109571.62	109788.92	KWH
HR SH Energy	310.17	254.44	KWH
HR DHW Energy	341.71	283.43	KWH
HP Startups	38706	33702	-
HR SH Startups	104	85	-
HR DHW Startups	164	124	-
Average SoC	40.52	43.12	°C
Average COP	3.79	3.72	-
PV-T Total Thermal Energy	26301.77	30262.85	KWH
PV-T Thermal Energy Used	23522.68	27639.12	KWH
PV-T Excess Thermal Energy	2779.08	2623.72	KWH
Ambient Thermal Energy Used	57165.89	52652.39	KWH
PV-T Total Electrical Energy	35548.81	35613.28	KWH
PV-T Electrical Energy Used	8684.37	10331.44	KWH
PV-T Excess Electrical Energy	26864.44	25281.84	KWH
Grid Electrical Energy Used	20850.56	19703.83	KWH
PV-T Thermal Efficiency	0.30549	0.30546	-
PV-T Electrical Efficiency	0.1282	0.1284	-
Total Duration of HP Operation	2787	2769	Hours
Duration of HP Operation - Day	1746	1808	Hours
Duration of HP Operation - Night	1041	961	Hours

The total thermal energy delivered by the system is slightly higher (103 kWh) in the case with the advanced control strategy as compared to the case with the control strategy 2. This can be attributed to the higher thermal losses from the hot water tank, due to a higher average SoC of 43.12°C, as a result of the increased temperature control limits of operation.

The number of startups of the heat pump decrease by 12.92% in the case with advanced control strategy as compared to the case with control strategy 2, due to the continued operation of the heat pump during the daytime when the PV-T system is operational. This is also reflected in the additional 62 hours of operation hours during daytime. However, the total duration operation of the heat pump in the case with the advanced control strategy is 18 hours lower, with a reduction of 80 hours in the night time operation duration. The higher temperatures in the hot water tank achieved during the daytime, meet the demands during the night time, reducing the necessity for the heat pump operation.

Because of operating the heat pump for a longer duration during the day, along with the PV-T system, in the case with the advanced control strategy, the total thermal energy gained from the PV-T system and the thermal energy from the PV-T system used by the heat pump, increase by 15% and 17.5% respectively, as compared to the case with control strategy 2. Consequently, the thermal energy of PV-T system that is lost and the ambient thermal energy used in the heat pump decrease by 5.6% and 7.9% respectively.

The total electrical energy consumed by the system, and that consumed by the heat pump, in the case with the advanced control strategy, increase by 1.7% (500 kWh) and 2.1% respectively, when compared to the case with control strategy 2, with the COP of the heat pump decreasing by 1.9%. This happens due to the higher temperatures in the condenser of the heat pump, with the increase in the temperatures inside the hot water tank at higher control limits. At the same time, the electrical energy generated by the PV-T system that is used by the system increases by 19% (1647 kWh), due to the synchronised operation of the heat pump and the PV-T system, resulting in a 5.5% (1100 kWh) reduction in the grid electrical energy used by the system.

5 Conclusion

The *tespy* and *tespy_Istage* heat pump models developed for this work, using the detailed thermodynamic approach, have been functionally validated against the *hplib* heat pump model, with the building thermal demands reduced by a factor of three. The three models supply similar amounts of thermal energy to the hot water tank over the course of the year, with a maximum difference of 150 kWh observed between the *hplib* and *tespy* models. The average heating capacities of the models however differ significantly, with the *hplib* model having the lowest heating capacities, the *tespy* model having the highest heating capacities, and the *tespy_Istage* model having heating capacities in between the other two models and closer to that of the *hplib* model.

The *hplib* model has the highest average COP of 3.38, and the *tespy* model has the lowest average COP of 2.97, with the average COP of the *tespy_Istage* model in between the two at 3.17. The *hplib* model overestimates the COP of the heat pump for most of the operation range, as compared to the curves from the manufacturer's datasheets. The comparison of the COP curves of the different models against the temperature lift, the source air temperature, and the condenser water outlet temperature, highlights the differences in the estimation of the heat pump performance by the *hplib* and *tespy* based models. The COP curves from the *hplib* model have an almost linear fit, whereas the COP curves of the *tespy* based models, have a non-linear fit that is expected from the literature.

Due to the comparable performance of the *hplib* model and the *tespy* based models in meeting the reduced building thermal demands, the *tespy* based models are deemed validated. The *tespy* model is found to be the most suitable model for the PV-T SAHP system simulations, due to its higher heating capacities that match the full building thermal demands, and a better estimation of heat pump performance at lower temperature lift conditions that are more likely when operated along with the PV-T system. The *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* model perform very similarly, with a difference in average COP of only 0.12%. The *fixed_evap_m* configuration of the *tespy* model is used, which allows the simulation of the PV-T collector system with a constant mass flowrate of air.

The PV-T SAHP system simulations, for the full building thermal demands, with the control strategy 2 with fixed temperature control limits, are performed for the baseline case with only the heat pump and for the different configurations of PV-T system with 2,4,6,8,10 and 12 panels in series and 133 strings in parallel. As the number of panels in series increase, the heating capacities and the average COP of the heat pump increase due to the higher source air temperatures achieved, leading to a reduction in the total electrical energy consumed by the system, and the share of the grid electrical energy used. However, the excess thermal energy and excess electrical energy from the PV-T system also increase as the number of panels in series increase. The relative improvement in the performance of the system obtained by adding more panels in series, reduces, as the number of panels increase. Therefore, the configuration of the PV-T system with 4 panels in series, with an increase in the average COP of 6.61% and a decrease in the total electrical energy consumed of 6.17%, as compared to the baseline case, is optimal for the building thermal demands in consideration.

The electrical performance of the system for the different configurations of the PV-T system, is compared with that of the system with only the PV component. For configurations with up to 8 panels in series, the electrical energy required from the grid is lower in the cases with the PV-T system, despite the higher self-consumption of electrical energy in the only PV system cases, due to the lower total electrical energy consumption. However, for higher number of panels in series (10 or 12), the grid electrical energy used is higher despite lower total electricity consumption.

The PV-T SAHP system, with 4 panels in series configuration, is simulated with the advanced control strategy, and the results are compared against that of the simulations with the control strategy 2. The mean temperature of the hot water tank increases by 6.4%, due to the increased control limit temperatures. Due to the higher condenser water temperatures, the average COP decreases by 1.9% and the total electrical energy consumed increases by 1.7%. However, due to the increase in daytime operation, when the PV-T system and the heat pump operate together, the self-consumption of the electrical energy of the PV-T system increases by 19% and the grid electrical energy used decreases by 5.5%.

5.1 Limitations and scope for future research

The different models in this work have been developed to simulate the performance of only one configuration of the PV-T SAHP system. The methodology for the development of the models could be extended to simulate other types of configurations, with different heat sources, different sizes of the thermal storage, an additional thermal storage between the PV-T collector and the heat pump etc., to study the change in the system performance. The control strategies used for the simulations could be modified with different limits, and additional control strategies could be implemented, to study the impact on the performance of the system.

While only the technical comparison of the different configurations of the PV-T SAHP system has been performed in this study, the comparison could be extended to include economic and sustainability criteria to gain key insights into the practical implementation of such systems.

References

- [1] “World Energy Outlook 2021 – Analysis - IEA.” <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2021> (accessed Sep. 19, 2023).
- [2] W. Weiss and M. Spörk-Dür, “IEA Solar Heating & Cooling Programme, May 2021 Supported by the Austrian Ministry for Climate Action Solar Heat Worldwide Detailed Market Data 2019 2 0 2 1 E D I T I O N Global Market Development and Trends in 2020.”
- [3] “Heat Pumps - Energy System - IEA.” <https://www.iea.org/energy-system/buildings/heat-pumps#programmes> (accessed Sep. 19, 2023).
- [4] A. Miglioli, N. Aste, C. Del Pero, and F. Leonforte, “Photovoltaic-thermal solar-assisted heat pump systems for building applications: Integration and design methods,” *Energy Built Environ.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 39–56, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.ENBENV.2021.07.002.
- [5] M. Scarpa, G. Emmi, and M. De Carli, “Validation of a numerical model aimed at the estimation of performance of vapor compression based heat pumps,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 47, pp. 411–420, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2011.12.011.
- [6] L. Gasser, S. Flück, M. Kleingries, C. Meier, M. Bättschmann, and B. Wellig, “O.1.4.5 High efficiency heat pumps for low temperature lift applications - HPT - Heat Pumping Technologies,” 2017, Accessed: Sep. 19, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://heatpumpingtechnologies.org/publications/o-1-4-5-high-efficiency-heat-pumps-for-low-temperature-lift-applications/>.
- [7] C. Arpagaus, F. Bless, S. Bertsch, A. Javed, and J. Schiffmann, “Heat Pump driven by a Small-Scale Oil-Free Turbocompressor – System Design and Simulation,” 2017.
- [8] “Projekt – ENaQ – Energetisches Nachbarschaftsquartier Fliegerhorst Oldenburg.” <https://www.enaq-fliegerhorst.de/teilprojekte/> (accessed May 15, 2023).
- [9] “Home | Olegeno Oldenburger Energie-Genossenschaft eG.” <https://www.olegeno.de/> (accessed May 15, 2023).
- [10] P. Durán *et al.*, “Technology pathways and economic analysis for transforming high temperature to low temperature district heating systems,” *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 11, pp. 1–24, 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14113218.
- [11] “JRC Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS) - European Commission.” https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/tools.html (accessed Sep. 22, 2022).
- [12] R. Heimrath, “Simulation, Optimierung und Vergleich solarthermischer Anlagen zur Raumwärmeversorgung für Mehrfamilienhäuser,” Institut für Wärmetechnik, 2004.
- [13] F. Witte and I. Tuschy, “TESPy: Thermal Engineering Systems in Python,” *J. Open Source Softw.*, vol. 5, no. 49, p. 2178, May 2020, doi: 10.21105/JOSS.02178.
- [14] H. Hoops, T. Tjaden, and K. Rösken, “RE-Lab-Projects/hplib: v1.9,” Jul. 2022, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.6792486.
- [15] “LW Serie | alpha innotec.” <https://www.alpha-innotec.com/de/warmepumpen/luft-wasser-warmepumpen/lw-serie> (accessed May 16, 2023).
- [16] M. Barsanti, J. S. Schwarz, L. G. Gérard Constantin, P. Kasturi, C. R. Binder, and S. Lehnhoff, “Socio-technical modeling of smart energy systems: a co-simulation design for domestic

- energy demand,” *Energy Informatics*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 1–13, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1186/S42162-021-00180-6/TABLES/2.
- [17] A. Mota-Babiloni, J. Navarro-Esbrí, B. Peris, F. Molés, and G. Verdú, “Experimental evaluation of R448A as R404A lower-GWP alternative in refrigeration systems,” *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 105, pp. 756–762, Nov. 2015, doi: 10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2015.08.034.
- [18] J. Gerster, M. Blank, K. Stern, and M. Sonnenschein, “Intelligentes Heimenergiemanagement – Nutzung der Synergiepotentiale bei der thermischen und elektrischen Objektversorgung durch modellbasierte und prädiktive Betriebsführungsstrategien - Tagungsbeiträge - VDE VERLAG,” 2016, Accessed: May 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.vde-verlag.de/proceedings-de/454308056.html>.
- [19] E. Saloux and J. A. Candanedo, “Modelling stratified thermal energy storage tanks using an advanced flowrate distribution of the received flow,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 241, pp. 34–45, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.APENERGY.2019.02.075.
- [20] D. A. Arias, A. C. McMahan, and S. A. Klein, “Sensitivity of long-term performance simulations of solar energy systems to the degree of stratification in the thermal storage unit,” *Int. J. Energy Res.*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 242–254, Mar. 2008, doi: 10.1002/ER.1344.
- [21] “Water - Thermal Conductivity vs. Temperature.” https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/water-liquid-gas-thermal-conductivity-temperature-pressure-d_2012.html (accessed May 11, 2023).
- [22] J. K. Tonui and Y. Tripanagnostopoulos, “Air-cooled PV/T solar collectors with low cost performance improvements,” *Sol. Energy*, vol. 81, no. 4, pp. 498–511, Apr. 2007, doi: 10.1016/J.SOLENER.2006.08.002.
- [23] K. Kramer, “Status Quo of PVT Characterization,” 2020. doi: 10.18777/ieashc-task60-2020-0004.
- [24] “How HOMER Calculates the PV Cell Temperature.” https://www.homerenergy.com/products/pro/docs/3.11/how_homer_calculates_the_pv_cell_temperature.html (accessed May 13, 2023).
- [25] “Air - Density, Specific Weight and Thermal Expansion Coefficient vs. Temperature and Pressure.” https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/air-density-specific-weight-d_600.html?vA=30&units=C# (accessed May 13, 2023).
- [26] “Air - Specific Heat vs. Temperature at Constant Pressure.” https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/air-specific-heat-capacity-d_705.html (accessed May 13, 2023).
- [27] C. Steinbrink *et al.*, “CPES Testing with mosaik: Co-Simulation Planning, Execution and Analysis,” *Appl. Sci. 2019, Vol. 9, Page 923*, vol. 9, no. 5, p. 923, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.3390/APP9050923.
- [28] “mosaik / components / data / mosaik-csv · GitLab.” <https://gitlab.com/mosaik/components/data/mosaik-csv> (accessed May 14, 2023).
- [29] “mosaik / components / data / mosaik-hdf5 · GitLab.” <https://gitlab.com/mosaik/components/data/mosaik-hdf5> (accessed May 14, 2023).
- [30] P. Kasturi and J. S. Schwarz, “mosaik-heatpump.” <https://gitlab.com/mosaik/components/energy/mosaik-heatpump> (accessed Jul. 24, 2023).

Appendix A

The data from the development of the *tespy_fixed_evap_m* model has been presented in section 3.2.1.2. Corresponding data for the other three heat pump models/cofigurations, i.e., *tespy_variable_evap_m*, *tespy_1stage_fixed_evap_m*, and the *tespy_1stage_variable_evap_m* models are presented here.

For the *tespy_variable_evap_m* model, the nominal operating point data (table 3.2), the Carnot efficiency plot (figure 3.7), and the heating capacity and power consumption data for the chosen design points (table 3.3), all remain the same. However, due to the changes in the parametrization of the model, the compressor isentropic efficiency map generated for the *tespy_variable_evap_m* model is different, and is shown in table A.1

Table A.1: Compressor isentropic efficiency map – *tespy_variable_evap_m* model

Compressor Isentropic Efficiency										
Source air temperature (deg. C)	Condenser outlet temperature (deg. C)									
	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60
-20	0.55	0.56	0.56	0.55	0.42	0.45	0.35	-	-	-
-15	0.54	0.56	0.58	0.58	0.52	0.54	0.48	-	-	-
-12	0.54	0.56	0.58	0.59	0.56	0.57	0.54	-	-	-
-10	0.53	0.56	0.58	0.60	0.58	0.59	0.57	0.52	-	-
-7	0.51	0.54	0.58	0.60	0.61	0.62	0.61	0.58	0.61	-
-2	0.47	0.52	0.56	0.59	0.63	0.64	0.65	0.65	0.67	0.59
2	0.44	0.49	0.53	0.58	0.63	0.65	0.67	0.69	0.69	0.69
7	0.41	0.45	0.50	0.55	0.63	0.64	0.68	0.71	0.77	0.78
10	0.40	0.43	0.48	0.53	0.65	0.63	0.67	0.72	0.77	0.81
12	0.43	0.41	0.46	0.51	0.62	0.62	0.67	0.72	0.80	0.83
15	-	0.41	0.44	0.49	0.59	0.60	0.65	0.71	0.79	0.85
20	-	-	0.42	0.45	0.53	0.56	0.62	0.69	0.74	0.86
25	-	-	-	0.42	0.45	0.52	0.58	0.66	0.68	0.84
30	-	-	-	-	0.37	0.47	0.54	0.61	0.62	0.81
35	-	-	-	-	-	0.45	0.49	0.56	0.56	0.77

The nominal operating point data for the two configurations of the *tespy_1stage* model is shown in table A.2

Table A.2: Nominal operating point data – *tespy_1stage* model

Parameter	Value	Units
Condenser inlet temperature	30	⁰ C
Condenser outlet temperature	35	⁰ C
Source air temperature	7	⁰ C
Mass flow of air in evaporator	7800	m ³ /h
Heating capacity	19.78	kW
Electrical Power	4.95	kW
Refrigerant	R448A	-

The Carnot efficiency plot for the two configurations of the *tespy_Istage* model is shown in figure A.1.

Figure A.1: Carnot efficiency vs Temperature lift plot – *tespy_Istage* model

The expanded heating capacity and power consumption data for the design points chosen, for the two configurations of the *tespy_Istage* model, is shown in table A.3.

Table A.3: Expanded heating capacity table of the heat pump – *tespy_Istage* model

Source air temperature (deg. C)	Heating Capacity (kW) / Power Consumption (kW)									
	Condenser outlet temperature (deg. C)									
	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60
-20	7.3 / 2.26	7.3 / 2.49	7.3 / 2.77	7.3 / 3.11	7.3 / 4.6	7.3 / 4.19	7.3 / 5.11	-	-	-
-15	9.5 / 2.65	9.5 / 2.9	9.5 / 3.19	9.5 / 3.54	9.5 / 4.5	9.5 / 4.57	9.5 / 5.37	-	-	-
-12	11 / 2.89	11 / 3.15	11 / 3.45	11 / 3.8	11 / 4.55	11 / 4.81	11 / 5.57	-	-	-
-10	12 / 3.02	12 / 3.29	12 / 3.6	12 / 3.96	12 / 4.75	12 / 4.95	12 / 5.68	12 / 6.68	-	-
-7	13.13 / 3.11	13.13 / 3.38	13.13 / 3.69	13.13 / 4.04	13.45 / 4.9	13.13 / 4.99	13.13 / 5.65	13.13 / 6.54	12.8 / 6.6	-
-2	14.75 / 3.13	14.75 / 3.43	14.75 / 3.74	14.75 / 4.08	15.3 / 4.9	14.75 / 4.94	14.75 / 5.52	14.75 / 6.26	14.2 / 6.5	14.75 / 8.63
2	16.34 / 3.13	16.34 / 3.48	16.34 / 3.81	16.34 / 4.16	16.97 / 4.8	16.34 / 4.98	16.34 / 5.52	16.34 / 6.18	15.7 / 6.5	16.34 / 8.18
7	19.39 / 3.12	19.39 / 3.65	19.39 / 4.07	19.39 / 4.45	19.78 / 4.95	19.39 / 5.3	19.39 / 5.82	19.39 / 6.45	19 / 6.6	19.39 / 8.22
10	21.5 / 2.86	21.5 / 3.69	21.5 / 4.2	21.5 / 4.63	22 / 4.8	21.5 / 5.52	21.5 / 6.04	21.5 / 6.65	21 / 6.75	21.5 / 8.34
12	22.6 / 2.35	22.6 / 3.57	22.6 / 4.19	22.6 / 4.66	23.1 / 4.75	22.6 / 5.57	22.6 / 6.08	22.6 / 6.68	22.1 / 6.75	22.6 / 8.29
15	-	23.75 / 3.11	23.75 / 4	23.75 / 4.56	24.3 / 4.7	23.75 / 5.5	23.75 / 6	23.75 / 6.57	23.2 / 6.7	23.75 / 8.05
20	-	-	25.5 / 3.28	25.5 / 4.23	26 / 4.65	25.5 / 5.32	25.5 / 5.82	25.5 / 6.35	25 / 6.65	25.5 / 7.65
25	-	-	-	27.4 / 3.47	28 / 4.6	27.4 / 5.1	27.4 / 5.63	27.4 / 6.15	26.8 / 6.6	27.4 / 7.35
30	-	-	-	-	29.9 / 4.6	29.15 / 4.68	29.15 / 5.34	29.15 / 5.89	28.4 / 6.6	29.15 / 7.04
35	-	-	-	-	-	30.95 / 3.79	30.95 / 4.89	30.95 / 5.58	30 / 6.6	30.95 / 6.74

The compressor isentropic efficiency map for the *tespy_1stage_fixed_evap_m* and the *tespy_1stage_variable_evap_m* models are shown in table A.4 and table A.5 respectively.

Table A.4: Compressor isentropic efficiency map – *tespy_1stage_fixed_evap_m* model

Compressor Isentropic Efficiency										
Source air temperature (deg. C)	Condenser outlet temperature (deg. C)									
	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60
-20	0.55	0.55	0.54	0.53	0.26	0.36	0.26	-	-	-
-15	0.55	0.56	0.57	0.56	0.44	0.47	0.42	-	-	-
-12	0.55	0.56	0.57	0.58	0.53	0.54	0.49	-	-	-
-10	0.55	0.56	0.58	0.59	0.54	0.56	0.53	0.45	-	-
-7	0.55	0.56	0.58	0.60	0.57	0.60	0.59	0.53	0.58	-
-2	0.54	0.55	0.58	0.61	0.60	0.64	0.65	0.64	0.65	0.50
2	0.54	0.55	0.58	0.61	0.63	0.67	0.68	0.69	0.70	0.64
7	0.54	0.55	0.58	0.62	0.66	0.69	0.72	0.74	0.84	0.79
10	0.58	0.57	0.58	0.62	0.73	0.72	0.74	0.77	0.88	0.85
12	0.69	0.59	0.59	0.61	0.75	0.73	0.75	0.79	0.91	0.89
15	-	0.61	0.60	0.61	0.74	0.72	0.75	0.80	0.91	0.92
20	-	-	0.64	0.63	0.69	0.70	0.75	0.81	0.90	0.95
25	-	-	-	0.68	0.67	0.68	0.74	0.80	0.87	0.95
30	-	-	-	-	0.57	0.68	0.72	0.79	0.81	0.95
35	-	-	-	-	-	0.77	0.75	0.78	0.77	0.95

Table A.5: Compressor isentropic efficiency map – *tespy_1stage_variable_evap_m* model

Compressor Isentropic Efficiency										
Source air temperature (deg. C)	Condenser outlet temperature (deg. C)									
	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60
-20	0.56	0.57	0.58	0.57	0.29	0.39	0.29	-	-	-
-15	0.57	0.59	0.60	0.61	0.48	0.51	0.46	-	-	-
-12	0.57	0.59	0.61	0.62	0.57	0.58	0.53	-	-	-
-10	0.56	0.59	0.61	0.62	0.57	0.59	0.57	0.49	-	-
-7	0.56	0.59	0.61	0.63	0.60	0.63	0.62	0.57	0.62	-
-2	0.54	0.57	0.60	0.63	0.62	0.67	0.68	0.67	0.69	0.54
2	0.54	0.55	0.59	0.62	0.64	0.68	0.70	0.71	0.74	0.68
7	0.52	0.53	0.56	0.61	0.65	0.69	0.72	0.74	0.85	0.80
10	0.54	0.53	0.54	0.59	0.70	0.69	0.72	0.76	0.88	0.85
12	0.60	0.53	0.54	0.58	0.70	0.69	0.72	0.76	0.89	0.88
15	-	0.54	0.53	0.56	0.68	0.67	0.71	0.77	0.88	0.89
20	-	-	0.55	0.54	0.61	0.63	0.69	0.75	0.85	0.92
25	-	-	-	0.56	0.55	0.59	0.66	0.73	0.80	0.92
30	-	-	-	-	0.45	0.56	0.62	0.69	0.73	0.90
35	-	-	-	-	-	0.58	0.59	0.65	0.66	0.86

Appendix B

The results of the validation of the *tespy* heat pump model developed for this work, for the simulations with full demands are presented and discussed here. The full building thermal demands, shown in figure 3.3, are used for the simulations of the system with the different heat pump models and their configurations.

B.1 Building thermal demands

The demand profile is shown in figure B.1, in terms of the heat supplied, as the demands are always fully met, either by the hot water tank or by the backup heaters. The space heating (SH) demand/supply values, available in kW, are shown directly. The domestic hot water (DHW) demands, available in L, are converted to corresponding power values using the flows from the hot water tank and temperature of the water supply and the incoming cold water for every timestep of the simulation. The thus converted DHW demand/supply values are shown in the figure. The total heat supply, calculated as the sum of the SH and DHW supply values, is also shown.

Figure B.1: Heat Supply/Demand Profile – Full Demands

The peak value for the total heat supply, averaged over a whole day, is 24.86 kW and occurs on day 347 of the year, as can be seen in figure B.1. The peak value for the heat supply in a particular time step, not directly reflected in this figure, is 108.03 kW. The peak values for the SH and DHW supply, averaged over a whole day, are 11.38 kW (day 46 of the year) and 16.72 kW (day 361 of the year) respectively, as can be seen in figure B.1, whereas the peak values for a particular time step are 32 kW and 96.03 kW respectively.

Figure B.2: Monthly Heat Supply/Demand – Full Demands

The figure B.2 shows the monthly aggregates, in kWh, of the heat supply/demand data shown in figure B.1. The peak values for the SH and DHW supply, 3704 kWh and 6640.36 kWh respectively, are both observed in the month of December 2020, leading to a peak value of 10344.36 kWh for the total heat supply. The lowest values for the SH and DHW supply, 2331 kWh and 5230.35 kWh respectively, are both observed in the month of September 2020, leading to a lowest value of 7561.35 kWh for the total heat supply.

As explained in section 3.3, all the configurations of the heat pump models are simulated to meet the same building thermal demands, and therefore they have the same heat supply profiles shown in figures B.1 & B.2.

B.2 Heat pump heat supply

The heat supplied to the hot water tank by the different heat pump models, is compared in figure B.3. The comparison of the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* models with the *hplib* model are shown separately, due to the similarity of the performance of the two configurations.

Figure B.3: Heat supplied by the different heat pump models – full demands

The heating capacity of the heat pump is dependent primarily on the source air temperature. Since these conditions are the same for both the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m*

configurations of the *tespy* model, the heat supplied is the same in both the cases. The *tespy* model has the highest heat supply of all the models, with a peak value of 48.44 kW, averaged over a day, and a maximum heat supply of 51 kW for a particular time step. The *tespy_1stage* model has a peak heat supply of 27.81 kW, averaged over a day, and a maximum heat supply of 29.15 kW for a particular time step. The *hplib* model has the lowest heat supply of all the models, with a peak value of 18.77 kW, averaged over a day, and a maximum heat supply of 19.33 kW for a particular time step. It can also be seen in figure B.3, that the *hplib* model does not supply any heat for some days of the year, the reason for which will be analyzed later in this section.

B.3 Hot water tank temperature profiles

The temperature profile of the hot water tank, for the simulations with both the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* model, is shown in figure B.4. The temperatures of all the layers in the tank, the mean temperature of the water inside the tank and the ambient temperature, averaged over a day, are shown in the figure. The heat supply of both the configurations of the *tespy* model being the same, the temperature profile of the hot water tank also remains the same.

Figure B.4: Hot water tank temperature profile for the simulations with *tespy* model – full demands

The temperature of the bottom layer of the tank (*Temp_layer_0*), is maintained between 40°C and 50°C on any given day, as can be seen from the figure B.4. However, over the course of the day, the temperature of the bottom layer does drop below 40°C, even when the heat pump is supplying heat to the tank, at the times when the heat demand is much higher than the heating capacity of the heat pump. As mentioned earlier, the demands for a particular time step go as high as 108.03 kW, whereas the maximum heating capacity of the *tespy* model heat pump is 51 kW. The heat supply from the *tespy* model heat pump is sufficient to bring the temperature back into the control range, after the demand subsides.

The temperature profile of the hot water tank, for the simulations with both the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy_1stage* model, is shown in figure B.5. The temperatures of all the layers in the tank, the mean temperature of the water inside the tank and the ambient temperature, averaged over a day, are shown in the figure. The heat supply of

both the configurations of the *tespy_1stage* model being the same, the temperature profile of the hot water tank also remains the same.

Figure B.5: Hot water tank temperature profile for the simulations with *tespy_1stage* model – full demands

The temperature of the bottom layer of the tank (*Temp_layer_0*), falls below the minimum temperature of 40°C, on multiple days in the year, as can be seen from the figure B.5. With a maximum heat supply of 29.15 kW for a particular time step, the *tespy_1stage* model takes longer than the *tespy* model to bring the temperature back within the range of control. In the summer months, between day 150 and day 250 of the year, the higher source air temperature resulting in a higher heating capacity of the heat pump, coupled with lower demands, allows the temperature to be maintained within the range of control, as can be observed in the figure. The temperature profile of the hot water tank, for the simulations with the *hplib* model, is shown in figure B.6. The temperatures of all the layers in the tank, the mean temperature of the water inside the tank and the ambient temperature, averaged over a day, are shown in the figure.

Figure B.6: Hot water tank temperature profile for the simulation with *hplib* model – full demands

The temperature of the bottom layer of the tank (*Temp_layer_0*), remains below the minimum temperature of 40°C, for most of the year, as can be seen from the figure B.6. With a maximum heat supply of 19.33 kW for a particular time step, the *hplib* model can bring the temperature

back within the range of control only on a few days during the year. During the periods of high domestic hot water demands, the incoming cold water brings the temperature of the bottom layer of tank below 10⁰C, the lower operating limit on the condenser water inlet for the heat pump. The heat pump remains turned off in this case, and can only turn back on when the temperature in the bottom layer rises above 10⁰C, with the inflow of water from the SH demands, at a temperature of 28⁰C, and an increase in the temperature of the incoming cold water for DHW demands, according to the sinusoidal function shown in section 3.1.3. In addition to these factors, during the summer months, the source air temperature ($T_{ambient}$) is higher than the bottom layer temperature. This results in negative temperature lift conditions where the heat pump cannot operate and it remains off until the source air temperatures reduce again.

B.4 Coefficient of Performance (COP) of the heat pump

The COP vs temperature lift curves for the different heat pump models and their configurations are shown in figure B.7.

Figure B.7: COP of the heat pump vs. Temperature Lift – reduced demands

The COP vs condenser water outlet temperature curves for the different heat pump models and their configurations are shown in figure B.8.

Figure B.8: COP of the heat pump vs. Condenser Water Outlet Temperature – full demands

The COP vs source air temperature curves for the different heat pump models and their configurations are shown in figure B.9.

Figure B.9: COP of the heat pump vs Source Air Temperature – full demands

The COP vs temperature lift curves, segregated based on the source air temperatures, for the different heat pump models and their configurations are shown in figure B.10.

Figure B.10: COP of the heat pump vs. Temperature Lift vs. Source Air Temperature – full demands

B.5 System performance comparison

The comparison of the performance of the different heat pump models is done using the KPIs shown in table 3.11, and is summarized below in table B.1.

As explained earlier, the *fixed_evap_m* and the *variable_evap_m* configurations of the *tespy* model differ only in terms of the electrical power and in turn the COP of the heat pump, with the electrical power consumption of the *variable_evap_m* configuration being slightly higher than that of the *fixed_evap_m* configuration. For the *tespy* model, a difference of 45.82 kWh or a 0.13% increase is observed, whereas for the *tespy_1stage* model, a difference of 37.31 kWh or a 0.12% increase is observed.

Table B.1: System performance comparison of the heat pump models for the validation scenario with full demands

System Performance KPIs	Heat Pump Model					Unit
	<i>tespy</i>		<i>tespy_1stage</i>		<i>hplib</i>	
	<i>fixed_evap_m</i>	<i>variable_evap_m</i>	<i>fixed_evap_m</i>	<i>variable_evap_m</i>		
Total Electrical Energy	36142.91	36188.73	32187.38	32224.68	59405.09	KWH
HP Electrical Energy	36137.98	36183.80	30990.91	31028.22	19164.04	KWH
Total Thermal Energy	110661.23	110661.23	110524.39	110524.39	110226.91	KWH
HP Thermal Energy	110656.30	110656.30	109327.93	109327.93	69985.86	KWH
HR SH Energy	4.06	4.06	828.26	828.26	28509.51	KWH
HR DHW Energy	0.87	0.87	368.20	368.20	11731.54	KWH
HP Startups	2464	2464	1038	1038	241	-
HR SH Startups	3	3	146	146	1424	-
HR DHW Startups	3	3	124	124	1316	-
Average SoC	50.62	50.62	48.10	48.10	33.32	°C
Average COP	3.062	3.058	3.528	3.523	3.652	-

The total electrical energy consumed by the system with *tespy* model heat pump is higher than that of the *tespy_1stage* model due to two factors. The first is the lower COP of the *tespy* model as compared to the *tespy_1stage* model, as seen in the figure 3.6. The second is the slightly higher temperatures in the condenser water circuit, reflected in the average SoC of the hot water tank. The total electrical energy consumed by the system with the *hplib* model is much higher than that of the other models due to the higher reliance on the backup heaters reflected in their energy consumption and significantly higher startups, due to the shorter time of operation of the heat pump as explained earlier. The shorter period of operation of the *hplib* model heat pump is also reflected in the electrical energy consumed, thermal energy delivered and the number of startups of the heat pump.

The total thermal energy delivered by the system with the different heat pump models is similar, with the differences resulting from the loss of thermal energy from the hot water tank to the environment. The highest average temperature of water in the *tespy* model case leads to highest loss and the lowest average temperature of water in the *hplib* model leads to the lowest loss.

The difference in the heat supply of the *tespy* and the *tespy_1stage* models is reflected in the number of startups of the heat pump. The higher temperature limit for the bottom layer of the hot water tank is reached in a shorter period for system with the *tespy* model due to its higher heat supply. This leads to more frequent switching of the heat pump operation. Conversely, due to a lower heat supply, the *tespy_1stage* model takes longer to attain the higher temperature limit of the bottom layer of the tank, and therefore has less frequent switching of the heat pump operation. The difference in heat supply of these models also leads to the higher reliance on the backup heaters in the system with the *tespy_1stage* model as compared to the *tespy* model, reflected in the higher energy and startups of the backup heaters.